

**BAHIR DAR UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS**

**THE SPATIOTEMPORAL DISTRIBUTION OF OZONE
CONCENTRATION OVER ETHIOPIA BASED ON SATELLITE
OBSERVATION**

**BY
ABEBAW BIZUNEH ALEMU**

**AUGUST 2024
BAHIR DAR, ETHIOPIA**

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ABEBAW BIZUNEH ALEMU

A dissertation Submitted in
Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of
Doctor of Philosophy in Atmospheric Physics

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DECLARATION

BAHIR DAR UNIVESITY
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DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS

I, Abebaw Bizuneh Alemu, hereby declare that the dissertation entitled "The Spatiotemporal Distribution of Ozone Concentration over Ethiopia Based on Satellite Observation" is my own original research conducted under the guidance and supervision of my advisors: Dr. Baylie Damtie, Dr. Jaya Prakash Raju, and Dr. Abdu Mohammed Seid.

I declare that all sources referenced in this dissertation have been appropriately acknowledged and cited. I confirm that this dissertation has not been previously submitted for any other degree or qualification.

Abebaw Bizuneh Alemu

Date ...23/12/2016 E.C

APPROVAL OF DISSERTATION FOR DEFENSE

BAHIR DAR UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS

We hereby certify that We have supervised, read, and evaluated this dissertation entitled "The Spatiotemporal Distribution of Ozone Concentration over Ethiopia Based on Satellite Observation" by Abebaw Bizuneh Alemu under our guidance. We recommended that the dissertation be submitted for oral defense.

For U. Jaya Parakash Raju
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APPROVAL OF DISSERTATION FOR DEFENSE RESULTS

As members of the board of examiners, the dissertation is examined entitled "The Spatiotemporal Distribution of Ozone Concentration over Ethiopia Based on Satellite Observation" by Abebaw Bizuneh Alemu. We hereby certify that the dissertation is accepted for fulfilling the requirements for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Atmospheric Physics.

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ABSTRACT

The existence of ozone in the stratosphere is crucial for protecting living things from harmful ultraviolet radiation. However, when ozone moves to the tropospheric region, it acts as a greenhouse gas, contributing to global warming, and can be harmful to living things beings when inhaled. Hence accurate estimation of ozone's spatiotemporal distribution is important for understanding temperature variations and preparing society for harmful radiation exposure. Therefore, this dissertation aimed to study the spatiotemporal distribution of ozone concentration over Ethiopia based on satellite observations. To address this objective daily total column ozone data of 108 observation points with spatial resolution $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ over the study area for the period 2012 – 2020 have been used. The spatial variations of ozone concentration over Ethiopian regions have been analyzed by considering the regions into longitudinal and latitudinal bands separately and investigating the sample mean difference among different bands using multicomparison analysis of variance technique to classify the regions into clusters.

The spatial analysis revealed that the distribution of ozone over Ethiopian regions can be classified into three clusters: Southern Cluster ($4.5^\circ N - 8.5^\circ N$ & $33.5^\circ E - 47.5^\circ E$), North-Eastern Cluster ($9.5^\circ N$ to $14.5^\circ N$ & $41.5^\circ E - 47.5^\circ E$) and North-Western Cluster ($9.5^\circ N - 14.5^\circ N$ & $33.5^\circ E - 40.5^\circ E$). This means that the ozone shield over Ethiopia varies from region to region with possible implication on impacts associated to these variabilities including exposure level to ultraviolet radiation and wind dynamics. We also studied the temporal variability of ozone layer over Ethiopia. The analysis has been carried out by decomposing the total column ozone time series observation as a sum of seasonal, trend and serially correlated noise components. This approach allowed us to separate the different components. The maximum total column ozone concentration found at 301DU during summer on August 18, 2013, while 216DU during winter on January 03, 2013, over the study period. The 95% confidence level of the overall mean of total column ozone concentration during the study period was found to be (261.35 ± 2.38) DU. In order to capture the temporal characteristics, we

computed the spectral periodogram for each cluster and obtained a power peak at frequency $f = 2.768$ millihertz, which indicates that the ozone concentration over the region exhibits an annual cyclic behavior. A truncated Fourier series fit is used to determine the annual seasonal component. The non-parametric Mann-Kendall's trend test with a 95% confidence level of significant indicated marginally decreasing linear trend over all clusters. The analysis of residuals for each cluster indicated that the residuals are normally distributed with no significant outliers and the model explains 85% ,86% and 79% of the variance in the North-West, North-East and Southern clusters respectively, demonstrating the reliability of the model considered in this study.

Tropospheric ozone level has been also modeled using SARIMA and additive Holt–Winters models over the North-Western cluster of Ethiopia using four homogeneous series of more than 13 years of data from ECMWF. We split the data set into training and testing sets. We used the data during the period 2007–2019 for model formulation and parameter estimation and the one year data in 2020 to test model forecasts. More than 60 SARIMA models have been generated for the time series. The best models has been assessed using the Akaike information criterion and Bayesian information criterion. We also applied model evaluation metrics such as root mean square error, mean absolute error and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) to compare the accuracy between Seasonal ARIMA and Holt Winters models. Our findings show that the best model for forecasting tropospheric ozone level is ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)[12] and ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)[12] for Addis Ababa and Ras Dashen stations respectively. However, for Danakil Depression and Bahir Dar stations Holt–Winters model with $\alpha = 0.346, \beta = 0.023, \gamma = 0.36$ and $\alpha = 0.302, \beta = 0.019, \gamma = 0.266$ respectively are found to be best models than the SARIMA. Moreover, the maximum MAPE were found to be less than 7.86% in the study & hence all the forecasts are acceptable.

keywords: Ozone, spectral periodogram, SARIMA,Holt–Winters

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Abebaw Bizuneh Alemu

DEDICATION

Thanks the people who really matter

ACRONYM

<i>AA</i>	Addis Ababa
<i>ACF</i>	Auto Correlation Function
<i>AIC</i>	Akaike Information Criterion
<i>AR</i>	Auto-Regression
<i>ARIMA</i>	Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average
<i>ARMA</i>	Autoregressive Moving Average
<i>BD</i>	Bahir Dar
<i>BIC</i>	Bayesian Information Criterion
<i>CH</i>	Calinski Harabasz
<i>CCD</i>	Charge-Coupled Device
<i>CV</i>	Coefficient of Variation
<i>DJF</i>	December January February
<i>DK</i>	Danakil Depression
<i>DU</i>	Dobson Unit
<i>ECMWF</i>	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
<i>FFT</i>	Fast Fourier Transform
<i>FOV</i>	Field of View
<i>HW</i>	Holt-Winters'
<i>JJA</i>	June July August
<i>JPSS</i>	Joint Polar Satellite System Program
<i>MA</i>	Moving Average
<i>MAE</i>	Mean Absolute Error
<i>MAM</i>	March April May
<i>MAPE</i>	Mean Absolute Percentage Error

<i>NASA</i>	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
<i>NEC</i>	North-Eastern Cluster
<i>NOAA</i>	National Oceanic & Atmospheric Administration
<i>NWC</i>	North-western Cluster
<i>nm</i>	Nano meter
<i>ODS</i>	Ozone Depleting Substances
<i>OMI</i>	Ozone Monitoring Instrument
<i>OMPS</i>	Ozone Mapping and Profiler Suite
<i>PACF</i>	Partial Auto-Correlation Function
<i>ppm</i>	Parts Per Million
<i>QBO</i>	Quasi-Biennial Oscillation
<i>QBO30</i>	Quasi-Biennial Oscillation at 30hpa
<i>QBO50</i>	Quasi-Biennial Oscillation at 50 hpa
<i>RD</i>	Ras Dasha
<i>RMSE</i>	Root Mean Square Error
<i>SARIMA</i>	Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average
<i>SOC</i>	Southern Cluster
<i>SON</i>	September October November
<i>SSN</i>	Sunspot Numbers
<i>SST</i>	Sea Surface Temperature
<i>std</i>	Standard Deviation
<i>SuomiNPP</i>	Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership
<i>TCO</i>	Total Column Ozone
<i>TOL</i>	Tropospheric Ozone Level
<i>TOMS</i>	Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer
<i>UNEP</i>	United Nations Environment Program
<i>UV</i>	Ultraviolet Radiation
<i>VOCs</i>	Volatile Organic Compounds
<i>WMO</i>	World Meteorological Organisation

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION	iii
APPROVAL FOR DEFENSE	iv
APPROVAL FOR DEFENSE RESULTS	v
ABSTRACT	vi
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	viii
DEDICATION.	x
ACRONYM	xi
TABLE OF CONTENTS.	xiii
LIST OF TABLES	xv
LIST OF FIGURES.	xvi
ORIGINAL PUBLICATIONS	xviii
1 INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background on Ozone Concentration	1
1.2 Motivation of This Study	4
1.3 Statement of Problem	6
1.4 Objectives of the Study	7
1.5 Significance of the Study	7
2 REVIEW ON STUDY OF OZONE IN THE ATMOSPHERE	9
2.1 Ozone Concentration	9
2.2 Review on Satellite Observation of Ozone	10
2.3 Ozone Density Variabilities	12
2.4 Seasonal and Inter-annual Variations of TCO	13
2.5 Solar Radiation	14
2.6 Ozone Depleting Substances (ODS)	15
2.7 Montreal Protocol	16
3 OBSERVATION AND DATA SOURCE OF THE STUDY.	18
3.1 Descriptions of Data Source	18
3.2 Selection of Satellite Data	19
3.3 Description of Used Data Source Instruments	21
3.4 Preprocessing of Satellite Data	23
4 SPATIOTEMPORAL VARIATION OF TCO	25
4.1 Introduction	25

4.2	Study Area and Data Source	28
4.3	Methodology	29
4.4	Result and Discussion	37
4.5	Clustering TCO Measurements over Ethiopia	49
4.6	Temporal TCO Distribution	54
4.7	Conclusion	68
5	MODELING SOL	69
5.1	Introduction	69
5.2	Study Area	73
5.3	Data Description and Methodology	74
5.4	Result and Discussion	81
6	CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS	91
6.1	Conclusions	91
6.2	Recommendations for Future Work	93
	BIBLIOGRAPHY.	95

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1.1	Composition of Constant gases in the Earth's Atmosphere	3
TABLE 1.2	Concentration of different Variable gases in the atmosphere	3
TABLE 3.1	OMPS Specifications.	22
TABLE 4.1	Daily mean TCO value at northern most & other latitudinal bands	38
TABLE 4.2	TCO daily mean value at 47.5°E and lower longitudinal bands	39
TABLE 4.3	Standard Analysis of Variance for longitudinal bands	50
TABLE 4.4	Longitudinal statistical variations of TCO measurements.	51
TABLE 4.5	Standard Analysis of Variance for latitudinal bands	52
TABLE 4.6	Latitudinal statistical variations of TCO measurements	52
TABLE 4.7	Statistical parameters obtained by multiple clustering	53
TABLE 4.8	Mean, Std and CV of variation over all clusters	55
TABLE 4.9	Mean TCO Concentration on Seasons	55
TABLE 4.10	Tests of goodness of fit for seasonal components	60
TABLE 4.11	Parameter Estimation for seasonal components	61
TABLE 4.12	Mann-Kendall trend test result over the three clusters daily data	62
TABLE 4.13	Mann-Kendall trend test result of three months mean desesonalized data	63
TABLE 4.14	Parameter Estimation for Residual components	66
TABLE 5.1	Geographical Location and Elevation of Stations	73
TABLE 5.2	Scale of judgement for model accuracy	80
TABLE 5.3	Exploratory data analysis of Monthly TOL	81
TABLE 5.4	Best ARIMA Model, Estimated parameter values	84
TABLE 5.5	Estimated parameter values of HW model for TOL	85
TABLE 5.6	Error Matrices of SARIMA and Holt-Winters models for TOL	87

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1.1	Thermal structure of the Earth's Atmosphere	2
FIGURE 2.1	GEO and LEO satellites (From brain kart)	11
FIGURE 2.2	Global Ozone Map	16
FIGURE 4.1	Data points of OMPS-NM satellite over Ethiopia	28
FIGURE 4.2	Spatial distribution of Mean TCO.. . . .	40
FIGURE 4.3	Spatial pattern of coefficient of variation (CV)	41
FIGURE 4.4	Monthly distribution of mean TCO over Ethiopia DJF-FMA	43
FIGURE 4.5	Monthly distribution of mean TCO over Ethiopia JJA-SON.	43
FIGURE 4.6	Seasonal distribution of mean TCO over Ethiopia	45
FIGURE 4.7	Comparative values of Ozone minima, 2013	46
FIGURE 4.8	Comparative values of Ozone minima, 2018	47
FIGURE 4.9	Optimal number of clusters	54
FIGURE 4.10	TCO distribution of NWC	56
FIGURE 4.11	TCO distribution of NEC.	56
FIGURE 4.12	TCO distribution of SOC	57
FIGURE 4.13	Monthly Mean TCO over clusters	58
FIGURE 4.14	spectral periodogram of the three clusters	59
FIGURE 4.15	Seasonal components of each clusters	61
FIGURE 4.16	Deseasonalized timeseries data with a fitted line	62
FIGURE 4.17	The three months mean deseasonalized data	63
FIGURE 4.18	Residual plots over NWC	64
FIGURE 4.19	Residual plots over NEC	65
FIGURE 4.20	Residual plots over SOC	65
FIGURE 4.21	ACF plot.	66
FIGURE 4.22	The Confidence interval of the model	67
FIGURE 4.23	QQ plot for Remaining Components	67
FIGURE 5.1	Monthly TOL (2007-2019)	82
FIGURE 5.2	Annual variation of monthly mean TOL (2007-2019).	83
FIGURE 5.3	Autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation function.	83
FIGURE 5.4	For SARIMA model actual and predicted data of training sets	85
FIGURE 5.5	For SARIMA model actual and forecasted data of testing sets	86
FIGURE 5.6	For HW model actual and predicted data of training sets	86
FIGURE 5.7	For HW model actual and forecasted data of testing sets.	87
FIGURE 5.8	ACF and PACF of residual data.	89

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ORIGINAL PUBLICATIONS

Original Publications from the parts of the Dissertation

- **Abebaw, B.**, Abdu, M., Baylie, D., U.Jaya, P.R. (2023) The Spatiotemporal Variations of Total Column Ozone Concentration over Ethiopia. **AIP Advances**, 13(11), <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0143718>
- **Abebaw, B.**, U. Jaya, P.R., Abdu, M., Baylie, D.(2023) Comparative Study of Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average and Holt-Winters Modeling for Forecasting Monthly Surface Ozone Level. **AIP Advances**, 13(3), <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0132812>

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- **Abebaw, B.** (2024) A comparative study on Bi-linear and Cubic spline methods for spatial estimation of ozone concentration. A-RIP Workshop 2024, **Boulder, CO, USA**. <https://s-rip.github.io>
- **Abebaw, B.**, U.Jaya. P.R., Abdu, M., Baylie, D. (2024) Identification of Total Column Ozone Minima Days In Ethiopia Based on Satellite Observation. International Conference on Pollution Control & Sustainable Environment (ICPCSE-24). Conference Presentation organized by National Institute for Engineering and Research (NIER) at **Darjeeling, India**. 06 July 2024
- **Abebaw, B.**, U.Jaya. P.R., Abdu, M., Baylie, D.(2024) Mapping Ozone Concentration over Ethiopia by Using Satellite Data: Implication for Atmospheric Sciences & Public Health. 5th International Conference on Eng. & Advancement in Technology. Conference Presentation organized by Malla Reddy Inst. of Eng. & Tech (A) at **Hyderabad, India**. 21-22 June 2024
- **Abebaw, B.**, Abdu, M., Baylie, D., U.Jaya. P.R. (2023) Temporal Variability of Total Column Ozone Concentration over Ethiopia. Seminar Presentation at Science Collage, Department of Physics, **Bahir Dar University**. 03 February 2023

- **Abebaw, B.**, Abdu, M., Baylie, D., U.Jaya. P.R.(2022) Spatial Variation of Total Column Ozone Concentration over Ethiopia. Seminar Presentation at Science Collage, Department of Physics, **Bahir Dar University**. 10 June 2022
- **Abebaw, B.**(2019) Estimating coefficients of Z-R relationship for Bahir Dar City Using Blue Nile Weather Radar Data. Abstract Publication on the Conference: **SPARC, Japan**.

Mega Projects During the study Period

- Abdu Mohammed, **Abebaw B.**, et al. A Mega Project on Investigating the Spatiotemporal Dynamics of Ionospheric TEC, Geomagnetic Field and Ozone concentration over Ethiopia using State-Space model. On Progress. (2023-2024)
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Other Publications During the study Period

- Abebe, K., **Abebaw, B.** Investigation of Spatio-temporal rainfall estimation using Hybrid satellite products. Journal of Applied Remote Sensing. Under Review
- Abebe, K., **Abebaw, B.**, U. Jaya, P.R. (2021) Examining the Role of Quasi-biennial Oscillation on Rainfall Patterns over the Upper Blue Nile Basin of Ethiopia. AIMS Environmental Science. 8(3), 190-203.doi:10.3934/environsci.2021013.
- Abebe, K., **Abebaw, B.** (2019) Identification of Rainfall Intensity by Using Bahir Dar C-band Weather Radar products. (IJCSAM) International Journal of Computing Science and Applied Mathematics. 5(2).
- Gera W., **Abebaw, B.**, Senait A.(2019) Ensure optimum profit using linear programming a product-mix of textile manufacturing companies. Int. J. Mathematics in Operational Research, 14(3).

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND ON OZONE CONCENTRATION

Ozone is an atmospheric gas. It is a tiny portion of the atmosphere that plays critical roles in making Earth's environment comfortable to human. It exists in two layers of the Earth's atmosphere: the stratosphere and the troposphere. The ozone in the stratosphere is an important ozone layer that effectively prevents living organisms from a harmful ultraviolet radiation emitted by the sun. The ozone that is present in troposphere is a bad ozone and considered an airborne pollutant. It is a secondary air pollutant that results from the oxidation of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) with the interaction of sunlight (Seinfeld and Pandis, 2016). Tropospheric ozone is one of the gases that constitute smog and has been found to be implicated in various health effects, such as respiratory and cardiovascular diseases and acts negatively on vegetation and the general ecosystem.

1.1.1 *Structure of Earth's Atmosphere*

The Earth's atmosphere can be divided into different layers based on temperature gradients. Troposphere is located from the surface of the Earth up to 8-15 kms. In this layer, the temperature decreases with altitude and weather phenomena exist and about 75% of the atmosphere's mass is located together with the majority of water vapour (Mohanakumar, 2008). Stratosphere extends from about 15-50 kms. This layer contains the ozone layer that absorbs the harmful ultraviolet solar radiation (Mohanakumar, 2008; Rowland, 2006). The mesosphere stretches from 50 - 85 kms above the surface. Thermosphere stretches from 85 - 600 kms and is marked by a strong warming with height. The final layer in the order extending from the top of the thermosphere to about 10000 km is called the Exosphere (as indicated in figure 1.1). There is also the transition zone between earth and space.

FIGURE 1.1: Thermal structure of the Earth's Atmosphere (Oceanic *et al.* (1976))

Temperature variation with altitude in the troposphere is decreasing, while it increases in the stratosphere and declines in the mesosphere; it is also returning to an upward trend in the thermosphere. The Earth's atmosphere is a mixture of gases, which is a natural formation that encompasses the whole planet and is vital in supporting life as well as moderating climate.

1.1.2 Atmospheric Compositions

The atmosphere is a mixture of gases that surrounds the Earth. The concentration of the gases varies from place to place. In general, it can be divided into the constant and the highly variable components.

TABLE 1.1: Composition of Constant gases in the Earth's Atmosphere

Gas	Formula	mixing ratio in %
Nitrogen	N_2	78.08
Oxygen	O_2	20.95
Argon	Ar	0.93
Neon	Ne	0.001818
Helium	He	0.000524
Krypton	Kr	0.000114

TABLE 1.2: Concentration of different Variable gases in the atmosphere

Gas	Formula	mixing ratio in %
Carbon dioxide	CO_2	0.038
Water vapor	H_2O	0-4
Methane	CH_4	0.000181
Sulfur dioxide	SO_2	trace
Nitrous oxide	N_2O	0.0000325
Nitrogen dioxide	NO_2	0.000002
Ozone	O_3	0.000002–0.000007

As shown in Table (1.1 & 1.2), constant components proportions remain the same over time and location, while variable components amounts vary over time and locations. Ozone is a tiny portion of the atmosphere and it is highly variable. It is a volatile gas that plays a vital role in controlling the chemical composition and climate of the atmosphere (Ashmore and Bell, 1991; Brown *et al.*, 2002).

Stratospheric ozone is formed by the interaction of solar UV rays with oxygen molecules and is maintained to provide protective absorption of harmful UV rays, while tropospheric ozone is polluted by photochemical reactions with NO_x , VOCs, and other major pollutants under the influence of sunlight. Understanding the interaction between atmospheric factors and solar radiation is essential to addressing ozone deficits and issues related to air quality, climate change, and ozone protection. The intensity and length of solar UV radiation are the most critical concerns in studying the concentration of ozone in a certain region.

1.1.3 Total Column Ozone

The total column ozone (TCO) is the total amount of atmospheric ozone up to the height of the stratopause and is measured as an integrated values of ozone over the column of unit cross-section. TCO at any location is found by integrating the ozone above the region, which covers the possible ozone layer. The TCO concentration amounting to less than 220 DU are usually considered as an indicator of ozone hole formation in the polar regions (Huck *et al.*, 2007; Pazmiño *et al.*, 2018; Fahey *et al.*, 2018). The ozone hole in Antarctica has gained worldwide attention due to its association with harmful effects of UV rays including cancer risks and effects on plants and animals. Over exposure to ultraviolet radiation from the sun is one of the major reasons for skin cancer (Saraiya *et al.*, 2004; Sivasakthivel and Reddy, 2011; Anwar *et al.*, 2016). Accurate assessment is essential for protecting vulnerable populations from the harmful effect of UVR exposure. Holm and Balmes (2022); Kim *et al.* (2020), also showed that high amount of tropospheric ozone levels can lead to significant health issues and environmental damage.

1.2 MOTIVATION OF THIS STUDY

Ground level ozone poses significant health risks, environmental and economic impacts. Individuals with asthma may face more serious challenges when exposed to high ozone levels. Exposure to ozone can increase symptoms of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, leading to more health care needs and a decrease in lung function. Ozone can affect the body's ability to prevent respiratory infections, making people more susceptible to illnesses like pneumonia and bronchitis. Premature death and decreased immune function have also be linked to exposure to ozone. Increase in ozone has been also associated with environmental and economic impacts like reduction in crop yield and affecting sensitive species to have reduced growth and reproductive success that affect the entire ecosystem. Harmful ozone levels are driving by using fuels in the cities and burning wood in both cities and urban areas.

Ethiopia has a diverse climate and topography. Systematic study of ozone concentration over different regions of Ethiopia can provide critical insights on key strategic intervention needed to mitigate any diverse effects associated with an increase in atmospheric pollutants. Sources of emission of harmful gases in Ethiopia are associated with rapid urbanization, industrialization and other economic activities that utilize nonrenewable energy. Also, the burning of crop residues and wildfires during agricultural practices release large amounts of ozone precursors into the atmosphere. The variability of ozone concentration over Ethiopian regions as a function of time has not been studied. The study of spatial and temporal characteristics of ozone concentration over Ethiopian regions is needed to assess any diverse ozone impacts. Data from satellites present to us great opportunity to study ozone over Ethiopia. Ozone monitoring instruments such as the OMI on the Aura and NASA satellites offer adequate high-quality ozone data.

The purpose of this research is to characterize the spatial and temporal variabilities of ozone concentration over Ethiopia using satellite data from period 2012 to 2020. We build on these spatial and temporal characteristics to model the ground level ozone concentration in order to offer predictive analysis to mitigate potential adverse impacts. This study provides a solid background and encouragement for researchers with interest to changes in the atmosphere as well as ozone impacts on health. It can also provide vital information to environmental policy makers to devise effective policies to mitigate air pollution. In health sector, this research makes it important to assess if there is an identifiable health issues in those areas with higher concentrations of ozone.

This research lies the foundation towards developing realtime and local ozone monitoring and early warning system in Ethiopia. Data driven models are increasing becoming critical. This thesis covered the first step in building self learning and adapting Ethiopian Regions Ozone Monitoring and Predicting System (EROMPS) with implication to health, environment and economy.

1.3 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Ethiopia requires rapid economic growth to bring its large population out of poverty. As a result, there is unprecedented urbanization and a strong push for industrialization that can lead to an increase of harmful ozone concentration due to increase in nitrogen oxides and volatile organic compounds (VOCs). It is critical to understand and monitor these dynamic changes and their impact.

Devising effective and practical environmental policy requires characterizing the existing realities scientifically. The dynamic of ozone concentration levels over Ethiopian regions have not been studied in detail. This thesis aims at bridging the knowledge gaps for environmental policy makers, health professional and other stakeholders on temporal and spatial variations of ozone concentration over Ethiopia using satellite data. The thesis presents a model of surface ozone in Ethiopia with implication to become an important tool for air quality forecasting and air quality control measures in the future.

The study also contributes to the ongoing global effort to map the ozone concentration accurately. Understanding ozone concentrations at a local level is critical in establishing a reliable global atmospheric model. Regional models have also potential to be more reliable for practical purpose in the region. Ozone concentration over the tropics is highly linked with the dynamics of tropical atmosphere. This means that the characteristics of TCO distribution over different regions of Ethiopia provides valuable insight about the underlying atmospheric dynamics. It is particularly important for seasonal ARIMA and Holt-Winters model forecasts.

This thesis addresses the following critical questions concerning the dynamics of ozone concentration:

- What is the spatial distribution of TCO concentration across different regions of Ethiopia?
- How can Ethiopian regions be clustered into subregions based on their mean ozone concentration?

- Which locations in Ethiopia experience the lowest TCO levels?
- How does ozone concentration vary temporally across different regions of Ethiopia?
- Which models provide the most accurate and reliable forecasts of ozone concentration in Ethiopia?

The following objectives were designed to solve the aforementioned problems:

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study is to map out the spatial and temporal characteristics of ozone concentration over Ethiopia. The specific objectives of this study can be broken down into the following:

- to assess the spatial distribution of TCO concentration over Ethiopia.
- to cluster Ethiopian region into subregions based on mean ozone concentration
- to identify TCO minima days and locations of Ethiopia
- to investigate the temporal variability of ozone concentration over Ethiopia
- to assess the performance of various models for forecasting ozone concentration in Ethiopia.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This research will serve as a foundation to trigger the development of ozone monitoring and early warning system for Ethiopian regions as well as new research on the linkage between ozone concentration and health risks in Ethiopia. In addition, it will have implication on environmental policy discussion, urban planning and alternative energy consumption. It also serves as the foundation to empower local community in dealing with regional and global environmental issues.

The findings will contribute to the global body of knowledge on ozone dynamics and inform regional atmospheric condition. By mapping ozone concentrations and identifying high-risk areas, this study will also encourage public health officials and policymakers to push for more research and understanding on the linkage of health risks with ozone exposure.

This thesis is organised into six chapters. Chapter two covers literature review and chapter 3 presents Observation and data sources, Chapter 4, discusses spatiotemporal variation of TCO, Chapter 5 presents the performances of surface ozone level forecasting models and chapter 6 contains the conclusions and future direction.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW ON STUDY OF OZONE IN THE ATMOSPHERE

2.1 OZONE CONCENTRATION

Many studies on ozone concentration lay the foundation for understanding of natural and human-made drivers for ozone concentration changes. These studies have indicated that tropospheric ozone levels were low before advent of industrialization (Banerjee, 2022). The increase in tropospheric ozone is associated with industrialization. The rise in tropospheric ozone has also been linked to the use of fossil fuels and automobiles. The observation of ozone depletion over Antarctica has sent a serious message to the world and it is due to CFCs (Solomon, 1999; Staehelin *et al.*, 2001). The ozone hole raised awareness globally about the environmental impact of chemical substances generated by humans. It led to a worldwide effort to mitigate the problem including the Montreal Protocol, an international treaty aimed at eliminating the usage and production of ozone-depleting substances (ODS) (DeSombre, 2000). This is one of the most effective global effort to prevent human environment.

For observation of ozone, satellites have been used to measure and monitor worldwide ozone concentrations. Stolarski (1988) used satellite data to show the problem of the Antarctic ozone hole and its association with man-made CFCs for the first time. The World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) provide regularly reliable information on the ozone layer's state, changes, and the efficacy of regulatory measures. Some of their publicly presented publications are based on satellite and ground data. Recent investigations (Petrescu *et al.*, 2018; Fang *et al.*, 2019) have shown that the destruction of the ozone layer is gradually being reversed due to the implementations of measures following the adoption of the Montreal Protocol.

Many research activities have been carried out to understand the effects of climate change on ozone levels. The relationship is complex. For example, climate change can affect the temperature profile in the stratosphere. Increase in greenhouse gases can lead to cooling, which in turn can slow down the chemical reaction that depletes ozone in the stratosphere. Other studies have also examined how El Niño and the Southern Oscillation (ENSO) activities affect ozone concentration (Zeng and Pyle, 2005; Benito-Barca *et al.*, 2022). ENSO can affect ozone concentration by impacting the transport patterns of the ozone. Others investigated the influence of human activities, such as the emission of ozone-depleting substances (ODS) and industrial pollutants, on ozone concentrations (Hough and Derwent, 1990; Rowland, 2000). There are also several studies that focused on the health risks associated to ozone concentration levels (Bais *et al.*, 2015, 2018; Barnes *et al.*, 2019). They have shown the health problems associated with extended UV radiation exposure owing to ozone depletion. The economic impact of ozone have also been studied (Fuhrer and Booker, 2003; Ashmore, 2005). These investigations have covered the ecological implications of ozone concentration, specifically how variations in ozone levels influence vegetation and agricultural productivity. (Thompson *et al.*, 1996; El-Tahan, 2018) have presented the temporal and spatial distribution of ozone over Africa. They have shown regional differences and the influence of geographic factors on ozone levels.

2.2 REVIEW ON SATELLITE OBSERVATION OF OZONE

Satellites have been used for various applications including communications, Earth and space observations, navigation and other technological development. There are multiple satellites around the Earth. The satellite tracking website identifies 9,900 active satellites in various Earth orbits and an increase of by thousands from the estimates by (Sannigrahi, 2017). These satellites are usually classified as LEO (Low Earth Orbit, 500-1000km), MEO (Medium Earth Orbit, 5000-15,000km) and GEO (Geosynchronous Orbit, 36,000km).

Polar-orbiting satellites belong to LEO satellites with the heights around 700 – 800kms (Sebestyen *et al.*, 2018). Polar-orbiting satellites move in a circular orbit that takes around 100 minutes to complete. Polar orbiting satellites travel from north to south. Geostationary satellites rotate the Earth above the equator from west to east. The revolution takes about a full 24 hours (Nimma, 2015). These satellites are located high altitude $\sim 38,500kms$ above the equator and used in communication and weather observations. Geostationary orbits are visible for 24 hours from the Earth's surface as its position is fixed.

FIGURE 2.1: GEO and LEO satellites (From brain kart)

Satellite instrumentalities and missions have been useful in the measurement of ozone concentration. For example, the Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) has been providing accurate information about the ozone layer, aerosols, and other factors (Levelt *et al.*, 2006) since 2004. The OMI, an advanced instrument aboard NASA's Aura satellite, gives us daily global measurements of key atmospheric pollutants. Burrows, J.P., et al. (1999) have presented the GOME instrument aboard the ERS-2 satellite that provides detailed information on atmospheric ozone and other trace gases. The SCIAMACHY instrument aboard the ENVISAT satellite that measures various atmospheric components, including ozone, has been published by Bovensmann, H., et

al. (1999). TROPOMI instrument on the Sentinel-5 Precursor satellite, highlighting its capabilities in monitoring atmospheric composition, including ozone, with high spatial resolution has been described by Veefkind, J.P., et al. (2012).

An integrated satellite data by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) has indicated the causes of all ozone depletions by the end of the 20th century and the first signs of recovery since the Montreal Protocol of 1987. Satellite observations have been very useful in observing the transport of tropospheric ozone, pollutants, and important greenhouse gases in urban and industrial areas. It has also shown how oxygen can be carried away, leaving behind carbon dioxide.

The distribution of ozone depends on radiative forcing as well as the temperature of the atmosphere. Direct observation of crucial processes including the formation and loss of the ozone layer by satellites has provided unprecedented opportunities to measure the concentration of ozone and increase our knowledge the dynamic process in the atmosphere. Satellite measurements can be validated using ground-based observations and other measurements to ensure accuracy and reliability.

Monitoring ground-level ozone is essential to maintaining air quality and protecting public health, as ground-level ozone is a harmful pollutant. Data from satellite observations have provided convincing information with implications to changes in environmental policies and triggering new international agreements such as the Montreal Protocol.

2.3 OZONE DENSITY VARIABILITIES

The study of the variability of ozone concentration is an active research topic worldwide (Chipperfield, 2003; Liu *et al.*, 2010a; Aucamp *et al.*, 2011; Ogunniyi and Sivakumar, 2018). Significant research effort has gone to study the spatiotemporal dynamics of TCO at both regional and global scale. For example, Chipperfield (2003); Harris *et al.* (2008) have shown a decreasing trend in TCO concentration in the middle and

high latitudes of both hemispheres during the late 1970s to the mid 1990s. Fahey *et al.* (2018) also have shown that the levels of ozone near the equatorial regions are lower than the global average value. Although the global mean ozone distribution of TCO is largely controlled by the large-scale stratospheric circulation, there is a large degree of year to year and shorter-term variability in tropical TCO Madhu *et al.* (2016). Ozone concentration levels can be affected by natural as well as man-made interventions. This means that the concentration levels exhibit spatial and temporal variations. Studying the characteristics of ozone concentration at a local scale plays an important role in understanding the local enforcing mechanisms and drivers including the associated health risks.

2.4 SEASONAL AND INTER-ANNUAL VARIATIONS OF TCO

Rafiq *et al.* (2017) analysed the seasonal and inter-annual variations of TCO over Pakistan region from AQUA-AIRS Level-3 Daily Global satellite data during 2003–2011. They used simple averages to determine the monthly, inter-annual and annual TCO variations. Their study has indicated that in Northern Pakistan region, $30^{\circ}N - 37^{\circ}N$, the maximum ozone concentration occurs in winter (DJF) season and the minimum in summer (JJA). Whereas, in southern part of Pakistan, ($23^{\circ}N - 29^{\circ}N$), they have shown that the highest ozone level was recorded in the summer while the lowest record was in the winter season. Chen *et al.* (2014) also investigated the spatiotemporal variability of TCO over the Yangtze River Delta, the most populated region in China, using TCO data from the Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer (TOMS) for the period 1978–2005 and from Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) for the period 2004–2013. They computed coefficient of relative variation for each latitudinal and longitudinal band to quantify the spatial variability and modeled the seasonality as an annual cycle with a sinusoidal function.

2.5 SOLAR RADIATION

Solar radiation is an electromagnetic energy emitted by the Sun, which reaches the Earth's surface and contributes to various processes. Solar radiation enters to our atmosphere as sunshine and some portion of the radiation is absorbed by the atmospheric substances; the rest of such radiation can be reflected back. Different events can limit the amount of solar radiation that reaches the Earth's surface. A wavelength of 10 nm to 125 nm ionises the air molecules, making them highly absorbed by air and ozone (O_3) in particular. Ionizing UVs do not enter the Earth's atmosphere significantly. The UVA spectrum is of no biological significance since it does not reach living organisms on Earth. There is an area of the atmosphere in which ozone absorbs around 98% of non-ionizing but hazardous UV-C and UV-B. The ozone layer begins at approximately 32km and rises. Some of the ultraviolet spectrum that does reach the ground is non-ionizing, but is still biologically hazardous due to the ability of single photons of this energy to cause electronic excitation in biological molecules, and thus damage them by means of unwanted reactions. Such hazardous UV radiation is controlled by atmospheric ozone through a continuous natural cycle of ozone formation and loss, called the Chapman Cycle Finlayson-Pitts and Pitts Jr (1999).

The Chapman Cycle describes the mechanism through which the formation of ozone in the stratosphere is balanced by its destruction through photodissociation. These cycles show how ozone is produced and sustained in a dynamic equilibrium. The detailed description of the Chapman reaction consists of four primary reactions:

Reaction 1: Solar ultraviolet (UV) radiation ($\lambda \leq 240nm$) dissociates molecular oxygen into two oxygen atoms.

Reaction 2: The oxygen atoms react with molecular oxygen in the presence of third body M (N_2 or O_2) to form O_3

Reaction 3: ozone absorbs UV radiation ($200 \leq \lambda \leq 320nm$) dissociates again into an oxygen molecule and free oxygen atom.

Reaction 4: An ozone molecule reacts with a free oxygen atom to form two oxygen molecules

Through Chapman cycle, a balance is created and sustained in the stratosphere in regard to the degree of ozonization. The rates of production of ozone through reactions 1 and 2 are equal to the rates of loss through reactions 3 and 4. This balance is crucial in sustaining the ozone shield that safeguards life from destructive UV-B light.

In addition to solar UV, human beings add different substances to the atmosphere that can potentially reduce the concentration of ozone layer (Parrish *et al.*, 1986; Ko *et al.*, 1994). The amount of ozone concentration in a region depends on the balance between ozone production & loss processes and the transport of ozone by atmospheric dynamics (Berbert *et al.*, 1977; Haynes, 2005). The ozone hole is defined geographically as the area where total column ozone amount is less than $220DU$ (Berbert *et al.*, 1977; UNEP, 2006; Standard, 2019). The combination of this low amount of ozone concentration with the direct overhead sun creates very high amount of ultraviolet ray over the tropics (Bais *et al.*, 2006).

2.6 OZONE DEPLETING SUBSTANCES (ODS)

The ozone layer is a region in the earth's stratosphere that contains high concentrations of ozone and protects the earth from the harmful solar ultraviolet radiations (Sharma, 2019). However, human activities, such as the release of certain chemicals known as ozone-depleting substances can lead to the thinning of the ozone layer.

FIGURE 2.2: Source: NASA Global Satellite Map of Ozone in 2009

The most common ozone depleting substances such as: chlorofluorocarbons, carbon tetrachloride, methyl bromide and hydrochlorofluorocarbons are the main reasons for the ozone hole. The Ozone Protection and Synthetic Greenhouse Gas Management Act 1989 governs the manufacturing, import, export, use, and disposal of ozone-depleting compounds. The Montreal Protocol mandated the phase-out of most ozone-depleting chemicals.

2.7 MONTREAL PROTOCOL

The Montreal Protocol, adopted on 16 September 1987, is a global agreement to protect the stratospheric ozone layer by regulating the production and consumption of ozone ozone-depleting substances (ODS). The Montreal Protocol was signed by 197 countries in 1987 to stop the use, production and import of ozone-depleting substances and minimize their concentration in the atmosphere to protect the ozone

layer of the earth. The first treaty was considered by many the most successful environmental global action. In general, there are five amendments to the Protocol: the London Amendment (1990), the Copenhagen Amendment (1992), the Montreal Amendment (1997), the Beijing Amendment (1999), and the Kigali Amendment (2016). As the ozone hole over Antarctica has in some instances grown so large as to affect parts of Australia, New Zealand, Chile, Argentina, and South Africa, there is an increasing focus on mitigating strategies.

The Montreal Protocol amendments are clear evidence of the international community's concern and active measures aimed at the preservation of the ozone layer and related issues. Another factor that has been helpful in the achievement of protocol conformity across the world is the flexibility and implementation of the policy aspect that deals with financial and technical support. The latest amendment of the Montreal Protocol is known as the Kigali Amendment, which was signed on October 15, 2016. This amendment includes hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs) in the list of controlled substances.

CHAPTER 3

OBSERVATION AND DATA SOURCE OF THE STUDY

3.1 DESCRIPTIONS OF DATA SOURCE

To study the concentration of ozone in a certain region, there are numerous data sources. Each of the data sources has its advantages and limitations. Data obtained from ground-based measurement, such as World Ozone and Ultraviolet Radiation Data Centre (WOUDC) and the Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) Program, offer high accuracy, which are crucial for validating other data types. Balloon-borne technology provides also high-resolution vertical profiles of ozone across different atmospheric layers. The other type of instrument is Satellite-based instruments, including the Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) on NASA's Aura satellite, the Ozone Mapping and Profiler Suite (OMPS), and TROPOMI on Sentinel-5P, which provides spatial and temporal coverage for global ozone dynamics (Levelt *et al.*, 2006; Veefkind *et al.*, 2012; Flynn *et al.*, 2014). Reanalysis datasets like ECMWF ERA5 and the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) integrate observations with model outputs (Hersbach *et al.*, 2020). Nevertheless, to the authors' knowledge, there is no existing balloon-borne and ground-based measurement data in our study area.

Choosing satellite and reanalysis data sources to study the concentration of ozone over Ethiopia offers several significant advantages. It is essential for capturing the spatial variability of ozone across Ethiopia's diverse topography. Satellites also offer consistent and frequent measurements, enabling the monitoring of temporal changes and trends in ozone levels on a daily basis. On the other hand, reanalysis data integrate the satellite observations with ground-based measurements. This integration creates a comprehensive, high-resolution dataset that allowing for detailed temporal analysis and trend detection.

3.2 SELECTION OF SATELLITE DATA

When studying ozone concentration over Ethiopia, several satellite datasets can be used with its own advantages and disadvantages. Below is a list of possible satellite instruments and their respective data products, along with an analysis of their strengths and weaknesses.

Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI)

- **Description:** The OMI instrument on NASA's Aura satellite provides daily global coverage of ozone and other atmospheric pollutants (Hersbach *et al.*, 2020).
- **Data Products:** OMI Level 2 and Level 3 products, which include tropospheric and total column ozone concentrations.
- **Advantages:** High spatial resolution (13x24 km at nadir), daily global coverage, long-term data record since 2004.
- **URL:** NASA Aura OMI

Sentinel-5 Precursor (TROPOMI)

- **Description:** The TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI) on ESA's Sentinel-5P satellite provides high-resolution measurements of atmospheric gases, including ozone (Veefkind *et al.*, 2012).
- **Data Products:** TROPOMI Level 2 data, which includes and total column ozone.
- **Advantages:** High spatial resolution (7x3.5 km), daily global coverage, advanced detection capabilities for tropospheric ozone.
- **URL:** ESA Sentinel-5P

Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment (GOME-2)

- **Description:** The GOME-2 instruments on the MetOp series of satellites provide detailed measurements of ozone and other atmospheric trace gases (Munro *et al.*, 2006).
- **Data Products:** GOME-2 Level 2 and Level 3 ozone products.
- **Advantages:** Moderate spatial resolution (40x80 km), global coverage every 1-3 days, long-term data continuity since 2006.
- **URL:** EUMETSAT MetOp GOME-2

Ozone Mapping Profiler Suite (OMPS)

- **Description:** OMPS on the Suomi NPP satellite measures ozone in the stratosphere and troposphere (Flynn *et al.*, 2014).
- **Data Products:** OMPS Nadir Mapper (NM) and Nadir Profiler (NP) provide total column ozone.
- **Advantages:** Daily global coverage, high vertical resolution for ozone profiles.
- **URL:** NASA Suomi NPP OMPS

Microwave Limb Sounder(MLS)

- **Description:** The MLS instrument on NASA's Aura satellite measures ozone profiles by observing microwave emissions from the limb of the atmosphere (Waters *et al.*, 2006).
- **Data Products:** MLS Level 2 ozone profiles.
- **Advantages:** High vertical resolution, daily global coverage, long-term data since 2004.
- **URL:** NASA Aura MLS

By considering the long-term records, high spatial resolution, frequent observations, data availability and accessibility, the advantages and disadvantages of each dataset, researchers can select OMI, OMPS and ECMWF as the most appropriate data sources for studying ozone concentration over Ethiopia, ensuring a balance between spatial resolution, temporal coverage, and the specific requirements of the study.

3.3 DESCRIPTION OF USED DATA SOURCE INSTRUMENTS

We selected the Ozone Mapping and Profiler Suite (OMPS) satellite data for ozone studies over Ethiopia due to its advanced capabilities in measuring both total column ozone and ozone profiles from the surface up to the stratosphere. OMPS, part of the Suomi National Polar-Orbiting Partnership (Suomi NPP) and NOAA-20 satellites, features three separate instruments: the Nadir Mapper, Nadir Profiler, and Limb Profiler. This combination allows for detailed vertical profiling of ozone concentrations, providing insights into the distribution and movement of ozone at various atmospheric levels. This is particularly important for understanding regional ozone dynamics in Ethiopia, which is influenced by its diverse topography and varying climatic conditions.

Furthermore, OMPS offers a high temporal resolution with daily global coverage, ensuring continuous and up-to-date monitoring of ozone levels. This is vital for tracking short-term variations and long-term trends in ozone concentration over Ethiopia. The OMPS data, validated for the study area by (Takele Kenea *et al.*, 2013; Chen *et al.*, 2013), using a high resolution OMI satellite data a make it a reliable choice for our study. The detailed description of data source instruments is presented as follow:

3.3.1 OMPS-NM

The Ozone Mapping and Profiler Suite (OMPS) is one of the five instruments of the Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership (Suomi NPP). It is the part of a Joint Polar Satellite System Program (JPSS), which is a collaborative program between National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and National Oceanic & Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) (Goldberg and Zhou, 2017). Suomi NPP was launched on

October 28th, 2011, has a sun-synchronous orbit with 13:30 ascending node, flies at a mean altitude of 824 kms and performs fourteen orbits per day (Jackson *et al.*, 2013)

OMPS is a three-part instrument with a nadir mapper (OMPS-NM), a nadir profiler (OMPS-NP) and a limb profiler (OMPSLP) sensors, collecting data since January 2012. OMPS-NM was designed to accomplish total column retrieval, using a two dimensional charge-coupled device (CCD). The spectrometer registers backscatter solar radiances every 0.42 nm between 300 to 380 nm, with a spectral resolution of 1 nm. The footprint of OMPS-NM is approximately $50 \times 2800\text{km}^2$, with 0.27° along-track field of view (FOV) and 110° across-track FOV divided into 36 cross-track bins. The two central FOVs cover $20\text{km} \times 50\text{km}$ and $30\text{km} \times 50\text{km}$, the rest, approximately $50\text{km} \times 50\text{km}$ each (Flynn *et al.*, 2004; Seftor *et al.*, 2014)

TABLE 3.1: OMPS Specifications

Parameter	Nadir Mapper	
Wavelength Range	300-420 nm	
Bandwidth (FWHM)	$< 1.1\text{nm}$	
Samples/FWHM	> 2.3	
Horizontal Cell Size	$< 50\text{km @ nadir}$	
SNR (Signal-to-Noise Ratio)	312.5 nm 1000	
	318.0 nm 1000	
	331.0 nm 1000	
	336.0 nm 1000	
	364.0 nm 1000	
	377.0 nm 1000	
	Polarization Sensitivity	$< 5\%$
	λ registration	$< 0.01\text{nm}$
Albedo Calibration	$< 2\%$	
Pixel to Pixel Calibration	$< 0.5\%$	
Albedo Deviation Error	$< 1\%$	
Stray Light (Out of Band)	$< 1\%$	

Source: <https://www.star.nesdis.noaa.gov/jps/OMPS.php>

3.4 PREPROCESSING OF SATELLITE DATA

To study ozone concentration over Ethiopia using OMPS (Ozone Mapping and Profiler Suite) and OMI (Ozone Monitoring Instrument) data, we need to follow a series of steps to download, preprocess, analyze, and interpret the data. Here is a detailed guide on how to process both types of data:

3.4.1 OMI Data

- Accessing the Data
 - **Source:** NASA's Goddard Earth Sciences Data and Information Services Center (GES DISC)
 - **Data Products:** OMI Level 3 for total column ozone of daily, gridded global data.
 - **Download Link:** OMI Data at GES DISC
- Preprocessing the Data
 - **File Format:** HDF5 or NetCDF
 - **Steps:**
 - 1 **Download Data:** Use tools like wget or curl for bulk downloading, or manually download from the GES DISC portal.
 - 2 **Read Data:** Use libraries such as HDF5, netCDF4, or PyHDF in Python, or similar libraries in R or MATLAB.
 - 3 **Extract Variables:** Extract relevant variables such as ozone concentration, latitude, longitude, and quality flags.
 - 4 **Quality Control:** Filter data using quality flags to remove invalid or low-quality observations.
 - 5 **Regrid Data:** If needed, regrid the data to a common spatial resolution

3.4.2 OMPS Data

- Accessing the Data
 - **Source:** NOAA's Earthdata.
 - **Data Products:** OMPS Nadir Mapper (NM) for total column ozone
 - **Download Link:** OMPS Data at NOAA CLASS

- Preprocessing the Data
 - **File Format:** HDF5 or NetCDF
 - **Steps:**
 - 1 **Download Data:** Similar to OMI, use wget, curl, or manual downloads.
 - 2 **Read Data:** Use appropriate libraries to read HDF5 or NetCDF files.
 - 3 **Extract Variables:** Extract total column ozone for NM , along with geolocation data.
 - 4 **Quality Control:** Apply quality control checks using the provided flags and metadata.

CHAPTER 4

SPATIOTEMPORAL VARIATION OF TOTAL COLUMN OZONE

The work is published in the Journal of American Institute of Physics (AIP): **Abebaw Bizuneh Alemu**, Abdu Mohammed Seid & B. Damtie, U.Jaya Prakash Raju (2023). The spatiotemporal variations of total column ozone concentration over Ethiopia. AIP Advances, 13(11), 115001. . <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0143718>

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Ozone is a chemically active colorless gas that reacts with many other substances. It plays a vital role in controlling the chemical composition and climate of the atmosphere (Kambezidis *et al.*, 1998; Rex *et al.*, 2004; Rafiq *et al.*, 2017). Ozone can be considered as harmful or good depending on its function. The function of ozone varies depending on its location in the atmosphere and its level of concentration. It is found primarily in two regions of the atmosphere. About 10 % of atmospheric ozone is found in the troposphere, the region from the surface of the earth up to $\approx 10\text{km}$ altitude, while the remaining 90 % is found in the stratosphere, the region between the top of the troposphere till about 50 km altitude. Stratospheric ozone is useful in absorbing the dangerous ultraviolet radiation from the sun and protects living things below it. Near the Earth's surface, the ozone's reactive nature can damage ecosystems when it is beyond the natural background level. For example, it can cause rubbers to crack, hurt plants and result in respiratory diseases in humans. It is important to study and characterize the concentration of ozone and its corresponding dynamics both at regional and global levels.

Total Column Ozone at any location is found by measuring all the ozone in the atmosphere directly above that location using ground-based stations and satellites. The total column ozone is the total amount of atmospheric ozone up to the height of the stratopause and is measured as an integrated values of ozone over the column

of unit cross-section. The TCO concentration amounting to less than 220 DU are usually considered as an indicator of ozone hole formation in the polar regions (Huck *et al.*, 2007; Fahey *et al.*, 2018; Pazmiño *et al.*, 2018). The ozone hole has gained worldwide attention and this is due to its association with harmful effects of UV rays including cancer risks and effects on plants and animals. Over exposure to ultraviolet radiation from the sun is one of the major reasons for skin cancer (Saraiya *et al.*, 2004; Sivasakthivel and Reddy, 2011; Anwar *et al.*, 2016). The study of the variability of ozone concentration using measurements and models has become a major topic of research around world (Chipperfield, 2003; Liu *et al.*, 2010a; Aucamp *et al.*, 2011; Ogunniyi and Sivakumar, 2018). The spatiotemporal dynamics of TCO at both regional and global levels has attracted the attention of many researchers. For example, (Chipperfield, 2003; Harris *et al.*, 2008) have shown a decreasing trend in TCO concentration in the middle and high latitudes of both hemispheres during the late 1970s to the mid 1990s. (Fahey *et al.*, 2018) also have shown that the levels of ozone near the equatorial regions are lower than the global average value. Although the global mean ozone distribution of TCO is largely controlled by the large-scale stratospheric circulation, there is a large degree of year to year and shorter-term variability in tropical TCO (Madhu *et al.*, 2016). Studying the variations of ozone concentration over a specific region plays an important role in understanding the environmental conditions including estimating the level of exposure to ultraviolet radiation.

Rafiq *et al.* (2017) analysed the seasonal and inter-annual variations of TCO over Pakistan region from AQUA-AIRS Level-3 Daily Global satellite data during 2003–2011. They used simple averages to determine the monthly, inter-annual and annual TCO variations. Their study has indicated that in Northern Pakistan region, $30^{\circ}N - 37^{\circ}N$, the maximum ozone concentration occurs in winter (DJF) season and the minimum in summer (JJA). Whereas, in southern part of Pakistan, ($23^{\circ}N - 29^{\circ}N$), they have shown that the highest ozone level was recorded in the summer while the lowest record was in the winter season. Chen *et al.* (2014) also investigated the spatiotemporal variability of TCO over the Yangtze River Delta, the most populated

region in China, using TCO data from the Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer for the period 1978–2005 and from Ozone Monitoring Instrument for the period 2004–2013. They computed coefficient of relative variation for each latitudinal and longitudinal band to quantify the spatial variability and modelled the seasonality as an annual cycle with a sinusoidal function. This study does not contain information on why the authors consider annual cycle in the seasonality in order to justify the reason for fitting the data with an annual periodic sinusoidal function. In such a study, determining a correct seasonal behaviour is crucial as the seasonality might also affect the trend analysis result.

In this section of the study, we investigate the spectral periodogram of the TCO timeseries to determine the power peak and the corresponding frequencies in order to identify seasonalities from timeseries data correctly. We are also interested in studying the spatiotemporal characteristics of TCO over Ethiopia using daily ozone concentration data from Ozone Mapper and Profiling Suite-Nadir Mapper. The objectives of this study can be considered as twofold. . The first objective is to capture the spatial variability of ozone concentration over Ethiopia and study the spatial patterns if there is any clustering of regions using the overall TCO mean along latitude and longitude through the difference of sample mean tests and multiple group comparison tests. The second objective is to understand the temporal variations using timeseries analysis of TCO of each cluster. The analysis is carried out by resolving the TCO timeseries into seasonal, trend and temporally correlated residual components. In order to optimize model performance and to capture regular, but non-constant variance changes between different seasons, we incorporate temporal correlations and seasonal variances in the model.

This kind of regional study on spatiotemporal variations of TCO can provide valuable insights on regional drivers of TCO concentration for many environmental and health related policy decisions. Since more ultraviolet radiation reaches over Ethiopian regions as compared to high latitudes Bais *et al.* (2006), continuous monitoring of the variability of TCO concentration is important. Moreover, ozone concentrations over the tropics is highly linked with the tropical atmosphere dynamics.

This means that characteristics of TCO distribution over different regions of Ethiopia provide valuable insight about the underlying atmospheric dynamics.

4.2 STUDY AREA AND DATA SOURCE

Ethiopia is located in the North-Eastern part of Africa, which lies approximately between $3^{\circ}N$ & $15^{\circ}N$ latitude and $33^{\circ}E$ & $48^{\circ}E$ longitude. There are four seasons in Ethiopia including winter (DJF), spring (MAM), summer (JJA) and autumn (SON). The topography of Ethiopia is highly diverse, with an elevation ranging around 125 m below sea level in the Danakil depression to 4620 m above sea level for Ras Dashen mountain range. The climate varies with altitude, from the arid climate of the lowest altitudes to the cool climate of the plateau. Understanding the spatiotemporal dynamics of ozone concentration over such a diverse topography and climate can provide critical information for environmental policy formulation.

FIGURE 4.1: Data points of OMPS-NM satellite over Ethiopia

In this study, we used different satellite data sources sampled at 108 observation points from the study area as indicated in Fig. 4.1. The OMI satellite data gridded with $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ resolution and Version 2.1 OMPS-NM gridded data with $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ resolution, both obtained from NASA Goddard Space Flight Center Website for a period ranging 2012 - 2019 (McPeters *et al.*, 2019). Takele Kenea *et al.* (2013), Chen *et al.* (2013), have validated the OMI and OMPS data sets respectively for the study area.

4.3 METHODOLOGY

4.3.1 Spatial Distribution of TCO over Ethiopia

The initial objective of the study involved a comprehensive assessment of the total column ozone concentration across the study area. This needed investigating the spatial mean distribution to understand the overall patterns and levels of ozone. The analysis has been carried out by using fifteen longitudinal and twelve latitudinal bands data over the region by considering measurement values along the same longitude as a longitudinal band and data values along the same latitude as a latitudinal band, respectively.

In order to study the longitudinal integrated temporal variations of ozone as a function of a latitude band, we denote the ozone measurements for the i^{th} latitudinal band at time t by $C_{t,i}$. We can then express the latitudinal and temporal varying measurement matrix \mathbf{C}_{lat} by

$$\mathbf{C}_{\text{lat}} = \left(C_{t,i} \right)_{2890 \times 12} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{1,1} & C_{1,2} & \dots & C_{1,12} \\ C_{2,1} & C_{2,2} & \dots & C_{2,12} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ C_{2890,1} & C_{2890,2} & \dots & C_{2890,12} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.1)$$

where $C_{t,i}$ is the longitudinal integrated TCO measurement over the i^{th} latitudinal band at time t , and $i = 1, 2, \dots, 12$ denotes the latitudinal bands that corresponds with $3.5^\circ, 4.5^\circ, \dots, 14.5^\circ$ North and $t = 1, 2, \dots, 2890$ represents time, which is the days of

the year in the study period from February 2012 to December 2019.

Similarly, to study longitudinal variations of ozone, we use the longitudinal and temporal varying measurement matrix, denoted as \mathbf{C}_{lon} , and it is given by

$$\mathbf{C}_{\text{lon}} = \left(C_{t,j} \right)_{2890 \times 15} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{1,1} & C_{1,2} & \dots & C_{1,15} \\ C_{2,1} & C_{2,2} & \dots & C_{2,15} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ C_{2890,1} & C_{2890,2} & \dots & C_{2890,15} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.2)$$

where $C_{t,j}$ is the latitudinal integrated TCO measurement over the j^{th} longitudinal band at time t , and $i = 1, 2, \dots, 15$ denotes the longitudinal bands that corresponds with $33.5^\circ, 34.5^\circ, \dots, 47.5^\circ$ East and $t = 1, 2, \dots, 2890$ represents time, which is the days of the year in the study period from February 2012 to December 2019.

To analyze the relationship between ozone concentration among bands, we used the coefficient of determination that explains the proportion of variance in ozone concentration from the concentration of other band which can be expressed by

$$R_{j,k}^2 = \frac{\left(\sum_j C_j C_k - N \bar{C}_j \bar{C}_k \right)^2}{\left(\sum_j C_j^2 - N \bar{C}_j^2 \right) \left(\sum_k C_k^2 - N \bar{C}_k^2 \right)}, \quad (4.3)$$

where $N, C_j, C_k, \bar{C}_j, \bar{C}_k$, and $R_{j,k}^2$ refers the number of data pairs, values of integrated TCO value for j^{th} band, values of integrated TCO value for k^{th} band, mean of TCO for j^{th} band, mean of TCO for k^{th} band and the coefficient of determination between j^{th} and k^{th} bands respectively.

4.3.2 Spatial Estimation techniques of TCO

The OMPS (Ozone Mapping and Profiler Suite) and OMI (Ozone Monitoring Instrument) satellites have the capacity for global coverage to assess ozone concentration distribution. However, there are unknown values between the grid data points that

require estimation. To address this, NOAA employs the bilinear interpolation method, which is computationally simple and fast. This method involves straightforward linear calculations, it is suitable for real-time applications and large datasets. However, It may not yield the most accurate results for datasets with high variability, as it only considers the nearest four data points and performs linear interpolation between them

In contrast, cubic method of estimation often provides more accurate results than the bilinear method. It considers more data points and fits a cubic polynomial, leading to better approximations. Cubic interpolation effectively handles variability and rapid changes in data, making it suitable for complex datasets. However, due to its higher computational complexity, it requires more computational resources.

Generally, We used cubic estimation technique for the spatial distribution of TCO concentration for areas that has no measured values between the grid points of (x_i, y_i, q_{ij}) along x-direction is

$$f(x, y_i) = \sum_{i=0}^3 a_{ij}(x - x_j)^i \quad (4.4)$$

and estimation along y-direction is also

$$f(x_i, y) = \sum_{j=0}^3 b_{ij}(y - y_i)^j \quad (4.5)$$

For the spatial grid data the over all cubic estimation is given by

$$f(x, y) = \sum_{i=0}^3 \sum_{j=0}^3 a_{ij}(x - x_j)^i (y - y_i)^j \quad (4.6)$$

4.3.3 Spatial Clustering of the Study Area

The characteristics of TCO distribution over Ethiopia are investigated by classifying the region into sub-regions or clusters based on the levels of TCO concentrations and by carrying out timeseries analysis of TCO for each band. We have classified the study area into representative sub-regions using spatial data clustering technique. We used

difference of sample mean tests of analysis of variance followed by multiple group comparison tests for the spatial clustering. We can now classify the TCO distribution over Ethiopia into sub-regions by assessing the existence of difference between the sample means. This is carried out by using the analysis variance technique (Kutner *et al.*, 2005; Hamada and Wu, 2000), which can be described by

$$F = \left(\frac{\sum_j n_j (\bar{C}_j - \bar{C})^2}{\sum_j \sum_t (C_{t,j} - \bar{C}_j)^2} \right) \left(\frac{N - k}{k - 1} \right), \quad (4.7)$$

where n_j , $C_{t,j}$, N , \bar{C} , \bar{C}_j , k , and F refers the number of observations on j^{th} band, values of integrated TCO value for j^{th} band at time t , total number of observations over all bands, overall mean of TCO, mean of TCO for j^{th} band, total number of bands and variation between sample means respectively. By comparing F values with the critical value of the F distribution at 95% confidence level, we can classify the observation points based on the result of analysis of variance into a particular cluster. The analysis of variance method tells us whether there is a difference of sample mean or not between the clusters. However, it doesn't tell us whether the concentration of total column ozone in one cluster can be explained by the concentration in another cluster.

Clustering Performance

Clustering validation has been recognized as one of the vital issues essential to the success of clustering applications. As discussed by (Liu *et al.*, 2010b) in their study, the effectiveness of using the Calinski–Harabasz (CH) index for cluster evaluation is significant when compared to other internal clustering evaluation metrics. This index not only provides a reliable measure for evaluating the compactness and separation of clusters but also demonstrates a robust ability to identify the optimal number of clusters. In this section, we focus on the internal clustering validation, as there are no ground data. The CH index is defined as

$$VRC_k = \frac{SS_B(N - K)}{SS_W(K - 1)}, \quad (4.8)$$

where, SS_B is the overall between-cluster variance, SS_W is the overall within-cluster variance, k is the number of clusters, and N is the number of observations.

The overall between-cluster variance SS_B is defined as

$$SS_B = \sum_{i=1}^k n_i \|m_i - m\|^2, \quad (4.9)$$

where, k is the number of clusters, n_i is the number of observations in cluster i , m_i is the centroid of cluster i , m is the overall mean of the sample data, and $\|m_i - m\|$ is the Euclidean distance between the two vectors.

The overall within-cluster variance SS_W is defined as

$$SS_W = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{x_i \in C_i} \|x - m_i\|^2, \quad (4.10)$$

where, k is the number of clusters, x is a data point, c_i is the i th cluster, m_i is the centroid of cluster i , and $\|x - m_i\|$ is the Euclidean distance between the two vectors.

4.3.4 Timeseries Analysis

Timeseries analysis for all the clusters was carried out independently from the mean values of all the observations in that particular cluster for each day of the year. Here, we decomposed the daily timeseries data from each cluster into seasonal, trend and residual components. We didn't consider other cyclic component in our definition as we are working with a short period of data (only eight years data). Hence, we defined the timeseries with additive components as:

$$Y_t = S_t + T_t + \varepsilon_t, \quad (4.11)$$

where S_t , T_t and ε_t are the seasonal or cyclic variation, trend component and residual components, respectively of the mean value data Y_t corresponding to each cluster.

The cyclic fluctuation of the timeseries is determined as the best fit of the daily measured TCO timeseries data (Fioletov *et al.*, 2008; Antón *et al.*, 2011). The seasonality

or cyclic fluctuation component of TCO timeseries is usually modeled with a one term Fourier series model (Schmalwieser *et al.*, 2003; Chen *et al.*, 2014). The main challenge here is determining the period of the cycle. We used power spectrum Fast Fourier transform (FFT) on the data to identify the dominant frequency. We defined the cyclic component of the TCO as

$$S_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i \sin(i \cdot \omega t) + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \cos(i \cdot \omega t), \quad (4.12)$$

where t refers the time in days of year, α_i , and β_i are free parameters to be determined from the data and $\omega = 2\pi f$, where f is the dominant frequency from FFT.

Before defining the trend, we would like to check its existence and behavior through non-parametric Mann Kendall test. The Mann-Kendall test can capture a highly significant trend (Libiseller *et al.*, 2005). The main advantage of this method is that it is not sensitive to outliers and the data do not need to conform to any particular distribution. The Mann-Kendall test is described mathematically as

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n \text{sgn}(X_j - X_i), \quad (4.13)$$

for

$$\text{sgn}(X_j - X_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } X_j - X_i > 0, \\ 0 & \text{if } X_j - X_i = 0, 1 \leq i < j \leq n, \\ -1 & \text{if } X_j - X_i < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4.14)$$

where X_j and X_i refer to TCO concentration at the j^{th} and i^{th} time respectively. The corresponding variance is

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{18}(n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{j=1}^p t_j(t_j-1)(2t_j+5)), \quad (4.15)$$

where p refers to the number of values with more than one occurrence (tied groups) in X , and t_j is the number of occurrences of the multiple value in the j^{th} tied group.

Then, the standardized test statistic Z is computed by

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{S-1}{\sigma} & \text{if } S > 0, \\ 0 & \text{if } S = 0, \\ \frac{S+1}{\sigma} & \text{if } S < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4.16)$$

The presence of a statistically significant trend is evaluated from the Z value and the null hypothesis is rejected if the absolute value of Z is larger than the theoretical value $Z_{1-\alpha}$, where $\alpha = 0.05$ is considered as the statistical significance level. The long term increasing or decreasing pattern of TCO timeseries have been modeled using linear trend in Africa (Oluleye and Okogbue, 2013). In this study, we also considered a linear trend for the eight years data, defined as

$$T_t = \gamma t + \alpha_0, \quad (4.17)$$

where γ and α_0 are the slope and intercept of the trend line to be determined from the data respectively.

To describe the serial correlation in the data and non-constant variance, we model the error term ε_t as a blocked AR(3) process, with periodic boundary conditions within each block

$$\varepsilon_{sn+k}^{(k)} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \phi_i^{(k)} \varepsilon_{sn+k-i}^{(k)} + v_{sn+k}, \quad (4.18)$$

where $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ is period index, $s = 0, 1, \dots, m-1$ is year index and v_{sn+k} is noise term with $E(v_{sn+k}) = 0$ and $\text{Var}(v_{sn+k}) = \sigma_v^2(k)$. The idea of modeling the serial correlated residual as in Equation (4.18) is similar to Cochrane-Orcutt correction in classical multiple regression (Hansen, 1995; Kyrölä *et al.*, 2013). Then using regression technique to estimate v_{sn+k} for the regression parameters ϕ_1, ϕ_2 and ϕ_3 , we can write Equation (4.18) in compact form as $\vec{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{E}\vec{\phi} + \vec{v}$. Then the parameters can be estimated as

$$\hat{\vec{\phi}} = \left(\mathbf{E}^T \Gamma^{-1} \mathbf{E} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{E}^T \Gamma^{-1} \vec{\varepsilon},$$

where $\Gamma = \text{diag}(\vec{\mathbf{1}}_m \otimes \sigma_v^2)$ is covariance matrix of the noise term \vec{v} with σ_v obtained from Equation (4.21) and $\vec{\mathbf{1}}_m$, a vector of ones of length m . An estimate of the noise term v_{sn+k} can be computed by

$$\hat{v} = \vec{\varepsilon} - \mathbf{E}\hat{\phi}.$$

Then, the standard deviation of the noise term v_{sn+k} is obtained as

$$\sigma_v(k) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{s=0}^{m-1} v_{sn+k}^2}. \quad (4.19)$$

The blocked AR(3) model used to represent the noise term \vec{v} can also be rewritten in matrix form as:

$$\mathbf{L}\vec{\varepsilon} = \vec{v}, \quad (4.20)$$

where the coefficient matrix $\mathbf{L} = I_m \otimes \mathbf{J}$ for an $n \times n$ matrix \mathbf{J} given by

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -\phi_3 & -\phi_2 & -\phi_1 \\ -\phi_1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & -\phi_3 & -\phi_2 \\ -\phi_2 & -\phi_1 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\phi_3 \\ -\phi_3 & -\phi_2 & -\phi_1 & 1 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & \ddots & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & -\phi_3 & -\phi_2 & -\phi_1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The relation obtained in Equation (4.20) is useful to ease computation of the inverse covariance matrix of the measurement noise during model uncertainty quantification.

Non-constant Variance

In order to ensure that the model parameter uncertainty is as correct as possible, we include the seasonally varying variance in the error term $\vec{\varepsilon}$ by approximating the standard deviation of the noise term v_{sn+k} by the trigonometric polynomial

$$\hat{\sigma}_v(k) = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^3 \{a_i \cos(2\pi ik/n) + b_i \sin(2\pi ik/n)\}, \quad (4.21)$$

where a_0, a_i and b_i are unrestricted parameters to be estimated by fitting the trigonometric polynomial to the model in Equation (4.19), so that this polynomial is strictly positive. Here, the reason to consider serial correlated noise and non-constant variance in the model is motivated as would be expected from the QBO, solar cycle, and other interannual variability in the ozone time series.

4.4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.4.1 *Spatial Variations of TCO over Ethiopia*

Understanding the spatial distribution of total column ozone is essential for studying its effects on climate and human health. Moreover, the study focused on examining both latitudinal and longitudinal variations of ozone concentration based on geographic location. By evaluating these spatial dimensions, the study aimed to provide a detailed understanding of how ozone levels fluctuate across latitudinal and longitudinal differences in the study area

4.4.2 *Latitudinal TCO Variations*

We have studied the latitudinal variations of TCO by calculating the daily difference of TCO value between the northernmost region of Ethiopia ($14.5^\circ N$) and the values at the other eleven latitude bands sequentially. We used the coefficient of determination parameter (R^2) using Equation (4.3). These yield the standard deviations and the coefficient of determination parameter values for latitudinal band differences as in Table (4.1).

The tabular values indicate that the statistical differences between the value of TCO at the northernmost latitude of Ethiopia and its value at other lower latitude bands increase as the distance of separation increases. The coefficient of determination parameter (R^2) between TCO value at the northernmost latitude and other bands demonstrates similar results. We can see that the values of the coefficient of determination measure the strength of the relationship between TCO characteristics at the northernmost latitude region and other latitudinal bands. An R^2 value > 0.8 means that at least 80% of the variance in the northernmost ($14.5^\circ N$) band can be explained

TABLE 4.1: Statistical parameters that depict the difference between the mean daily TCO value at northern most latitude ($14.5^{\circ}N$) and other latitudinal bands over Ethiopia

Latitude	Std	$ \mu_1 - \mu_2 $	R^2
$14.5^{\circ}N - 13.5^{\circ}N$	1.6	0.5	0.989
$14.5^{\circ}N - 12.5^{\circ}N$	2.7	1.57	0.969
$14.5^{\circ}N - 11.5^{\circ}N$	3.74	3.29	0.942
$14.5^{\circ}N - 10.5^{\circ}N$	4.75	3.56	0.907
$14.5^{\circ}N - 9.5^{\circ}N$	5.75	3.71	0.864
$14.5^{\circ}N - 8.5^{\circ}N$	6.77	3.5	0.809
$14.5^{\circ}N - 7.5^{\circ}N$	7.78	3.0	0.742
$14.5^{\circ}N - 6.5^{\circ}N$	8.74	2.73	0.668
$14.5^{\circ}N - 5.5^{\circ}N$	9.58	1.86	0.596
$14.5^{\circ}N - 4.5^{\circ}N$	10.39	1.8	0.526
$14.5^{\circ}N - 3.5^{\circ}N$	11.14	0.86	0.461

by the variance in the compared band. Choosing 80% as a criterion for statistical representativeness Akoglu (2018). The observations at ($14.5^{\circ}N$) can be described by variations in latitude bands down to 8.5° indicating similarities in TCO values over 6° latitude coverage.

4.4.3 Longitudinal TCO Variation

Similarly, the longitudinal variations of TCO have been investigated by evaluating the statistical difference between the mean daily value of TCO observed over the most Eastern tip of Ethiopia ($47.5^{\circ}E$) and TCO values over other lower longitudinal regions. Table (4.2) shows the standard deviations, mean difference and the coefficient of determination (R^2) for the respective bands.

TABLE 4.2: Statistical parameters that depict the difference between TCO daily mean value at $47.5^{\circ}E$ and its value at other lower longitudinal bands.

Longitude	Std	$ \mu_1 - \mu_2 $	R^2
$47.5^{\circ}E - 46.5^{\circ}E$	2.91	1.01	0.946
$47.5^{\circ}E - 45.5^{\circ}E$	2.21	0.45	0.969
$47.5^{\circ}E - 44.5^{\circ}E$	3.47	1.80	0.924
$47.5^{\circ}E - 43.5^{\circ}E$	3.11	1.49	0.939
$47.5^{\circ}E - 42.5^{\circ}E$	4.09	1.85	0.895
$47.5^{\circ}E - 41.5^{\circ}E$	4.2	0.54	0.893
$47.5^{\circ}E - 40.5^{\circ}E$	4.73	5.48	0.863
$47.5^{\circ}E - 39.5^{\circ}E$	4.59	1.98	0.871
$47.5^{\circ}E - 38.5^{\circ}E$	4.83	5.2	0.854
$47.5^{\circ}E - 37.5^{\circ}E$	4.88	6.26	0.855
$47.5^{\circ}E - 36.5^{\circ}E$	5.27	2.83	0.825
$47.5^{\circ}E - 35.5^{\circ}E$	5.1	5.18	0.836
$47.5^{\circ}E - 34.5^{\circ}E$	5.95	1.08	0.777
$47.5^{\circ}E - 33.5^{\circ}E$	5.87	2.67	0.783

Table (4.2) shows that for most longitudes, values of R^2 are greater than 0.8 with the lowest value of 0.777. This means at least 77% of the variability in the observation at 47.5° can be represented from TCO observations up to 33.5° . To analyze the latitudinal and longitudinal variations of TCO concentration in a region, we utilized a spatial mean TCO distribution plot. This method allowed us to visualize the geographic distribution of TCO levels across various latitudes and longitudes. By examining the spatial mean, we could identify specific areas with higher or lower concentrations of TCO, providing valuable insights into the regional patterns.

4.4.4 Spatial Estimation of TCO

Spatial estimation of TCO involves using various techniques to measure and map ozone concentration in the atmosphere across different geographical regions. The bilinear estimation method is widely known for its simplicity, speed, and efficiency, making it suitable for real-time applications with limited resources. On the other hand, the cubic estimation method offers higher accuracy and smoother results, making it ideal for applications where these qualities are crucial, despite its higher computational cost. Due to its accuracy and ability to precisely identify extreme ozone values

in spatial data, the cubic estimation technique is preferred despite its computational complexity. The NOAA employs the bilinear estimation technique using the four nearest data points with measured values. However, for areas without measurement values, we used cubic estimation, considering 16 nearest data points. To address boundary issues, we also collected data from points outside Ethiopia's borders.

4.4.5 Spatial Mean of TCO over Ethiopia

The spatial overall mean of total column ozone is a measure of the average ozone concentration across a given geographical area. This mean provides insights into the general state of ozone distribution and highlight regions with higher or lower than average ozone concentrations.

FIGURE 4.2: Spatial distribution of Mean TCO.

Figure (4.2) shows high mean TCO concentration over the Northern part of Ethiopia and low concentration over the southern part of Ethiopia. This overall local increasing TCO variation result along latitude is inline with the global spatial TCO variation

study (Stein, 2007). Moreover, the relation between TCO distributions with meteorological variables over the region might need a thorough investigation with state-of-the-art methods like Graeco-Latin square and we leave this for a future study.

4.4.6 Spatial Variance of Total Column Ozone

The spatial variance of total column ozone quantifies the degree of variation or dispersion of ozone values across the geographical area. High variance indicates significant differences in ozone concentrations between regions, while low variance suggests a more uniform distribution. In addition to the overall mean TCO variation the variability of TCO concentration over the study area is also assessed by calculating the coefficient of variation as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean for each data point as shown in Figure (4.3) using the overall mean TCO value.

FIGURE 4.3: Spatial pattern of coefficient of variation (CV)

Figure (4.3) shows the variability of TCO concentration during the study period and it is found to be between 4.75% and 5.7%. One can see a relatively lower variations in the South-Eastern part of Ethiopia. The mean TCO concentration in the Northern and Central parts of Ethiopia is relatively higher than the concentration in most of the Southern parts of Ethiopia.

The presence of relatively low total column ozone concentration and low variation in the southern part of Ethiopia could be influenced by various factors. One possible reason is the geographical location and topography of the region. The southern part of Ethiopia may experience different atmospheric conditions compared to other areas, such as lower elevation or proximity to certain air masses. These factors can affect the distribution and concentration of ozone in the atmosphere.

Additionally, meteorological conditions, such as temperature and wind patterns can also play a role in ozone concentration. Certain weather patterns or atmospheric phenomena in the southern part of Ethiopia may contribute to lower ozone levels. It is important to note that specific data and analysis would be required to provide a more accurate explanation for the observed low total column ozone concentration in the southern part of Ethiopia.

4.4.7 *Monthly TCO Concentration*

As ozone is varying due to different factors, among those factors understanding the monthly variability is one of the most crucial. It allows for a comparative analysis between different months. This can highlight specific periods when ozone concentration is particularly low or high, helping to identify potential causes or correlations with other environmental factors such as pollution levels, meteorological conditions, or agricultural practices.

FIGURE 4.4: Monthly distribution of mean TCO over Ethiopia a) December b) January c) February d) March e) April f) May

FIGURE 4.5: Monthly distribution of mean TCO over Ethiopia a) June b) July c) August d) September e) October f) November

As we have seen figure (4.4 & 4.5), the maximum total column ozone concentration was recorded during June, July and August months. While, the minimum was recorded during December, January and February months.

4.4.8 *TCO Concentration over Seasons*

We have studied the spatial TCO concentration over the study area by considering the overall temporal mean of every data point for all four seasons of Ethiopia including winter, spring, summer and autumn.

Figure (4.6) shows the spatial distribution of TCO over Ethiopia for each season. High-latitude regions have a relative maximum TCO while low-latitudes experienced minimum values. The result is identical with (Stein, 2007). We can see that a relative maximum TCO concentration has been observed during the Summer (JJA) and a minimum concentration during the Winter (DJF) season. During June, July, and August, Ethiopia experiences its main rainy season, which might be influenced by various atmospheric dynamics that lead to high TCO. Large-scale atmospheric Circulation Patterns, influenced by the Earth's tilt and seasonal changes can support the vertical transport of ozone, this might also contributing to enhancing higher the total column ozone.

4.4.9 *Minimum TCO Concentration*

The global mean ozone concentration is approximately 300 DU (Bekki and Lefèvre, 2009). We have found that the mean TCO concentration over the study area was below this global average. In the study period considered, the concentration of TCO was found to be in the range between 216-301 DU, where some are below the threshold concentration 220 DU though the frequency is insignificant. These low TCO values can be a concern and an indication to explore mitigation strategies. Also, it is useful to apply more reliable spatiotemporal analysis technique to investigate TCO concentrations in the region. It is important to notice that a value of 220 DU is considered as the baseline value for an indicator of ozone hole formation (Berbert

FIGURE 4.6: Seasonal distribution of mean TCO over Ethiopia from 2012-2019, note that there is a scale difference in the seasonal panels. a: Winter(DJF), b: Spring(MAM), c: Summer(JJA), and d= Autumn(SON).

et al., 1977; Standard, 2019). We have found that some recorded values below this baseline in the study area and need to be considered seriously.

FIGURE 4.7: Comparative values of Ozone minima the left is satellite measurement, the middle is Bi-linear and the right one is cubic-spline estimations during 2013

FIGURE 4.8: Comparative values of Ozone minima the left is satellite measurement, the middle is Bi-linear and the right one is cubic-spline estimations during 2018

Figure (4.7) depicts the minimum TCO concentration and corresponding date of occurrence. It shows the satellite ozone measurement and its estimation using linear and cubic spline methods for different dates in January 2013 & December, 2018. To

analyze the validation of the linear and cubic spline estimation methods against the satellite measurement values for different dates of ozone minima, by comparing the estimations with the satellite measurement:

- Satellite Measurement
 - Shows localized ozone concentrations below 220 DU.
- Linear Estimation
 - Tends to smooth out variations, providing a more averaged and generalized representation of the ozone concentration. It often misses localized peaks and troughs seen in the satellite measurements.
- Cubic Spline Estimation
 - Provides a closer match to the satellite measurements, accurately capturing localized variations and offering a more detailed representation of ozone concentration.

The study compares the bi-linear and cubic spline estimates to identify local minimum TCO values through Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) performance measure. The MAPE of estimates are 3.18%, 1.89% for the bi-linear and cubic splines respectively. Even if, all results were in an acceptable range, the finding leads to propose cubic spline estimates. In general, the cubic spline estimation method consistently validates better against the satellite measurements for the given dates, making it a more reliable method for estimating ozone concentrations.

Figure 4.7 & 4.8 show that total column ozone concentration over Ethiopia being below the baseline of 220DU during January 2013 and December 2018 could be attributed to various factors. Although the frequency is low, we have seen that the recorded values for ozone concentration are significantly lower than those reported in (Berbert *et al.*, 1977). Some possible reasons for this observation could include natural variations in atmospheric conditions, such as changes in weather patterns

or atmospheric circulation. Additionally, human activities, such as the release of ozone-depleting substances or pollution, could also contribute to lower ozone concentrations.

Based on this study and the results of other researchers over Kenya, West Africa and Pakistan (Oluleye and Okogbue, 2013; Madhu *et al.*, 2016; Rafiq *et al.*, 2017; Songa, 2017), the source of seasonal variability of ozone distribution over Ethiopia may be mainly due to ozone transport and chemistry. However, in order to reach a more strong conclusion, the impact of Quasi Benian Oscillation (QBO) and Solar UV radiation on the variability of ozone over Ethiopia should be studied in detail.

4.5 CLUSTERING TCO MEASUREMENTS OVER ETHIOPIA

It is practical to classify all data points into representative sub-regions and investigate the distribution of TCO measurements at different topographical and climate zones of Ethiopia. We carried out the clustering of TCO values for the study area using Equation (4.7). We give discussion for the longitudinal and latitudinal clusters in detail in the subsequent subsections.

4.5.1 *Longitudinal Clustering*

We used the null hypothesis to classify the TCO corresponding to a specific longitudinal band. We defined the null hypothesis here as follows.

- H_0 : There is no mean difference between any two longitudinal bands,
- H_1 : There is mean difference at least between two of the longitudinal bands.

We test for differences in the longitudinal sample means by computing the F value from Equation (4.7) and comparing it against the distribution of F values valid for the null hypothesis, which is defined as no longitudinal band sample mean is significantly different than any other longitudinal band sample mean. If the computed F-value is more extreme than 95% of the null hypothesis distribution (p -value < 0.05) we reject the null hypothesis. If the null hypothesis is rejected, we then carry out a multiple

comparison technique to identify which longitudinal sample means are different and which are similar to define the clusters. Table (4.3) shows the individual terms from Equation (4.7) and the resulting F-value and p-value. The p-value is less than 0.05 so we reject the null hypothesis. In Table (4.3), the total degree of freedom is 40614 due to the missing data values in C_{lon} (Eqn 4.2) that can't be replaced with the linear interpolation. Table (4.4) shows the results from the multiple comparison technique Since F (95%) is the F-value corresponding to $P=0.05$ and an F-value more extreme

TABLE 4.3: Standard Analysis of Variance for longitudinal bands (C_{lon}) (Eqn 4.2, $k=15$, $N=2890 \times 15$). Results demonstrate mean difference among the longitudinal bands

Source of Variation	Sum square	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares	F	P
Between bands (Groups)	13867	14	990.3	67.06	< 0.001
Within bands (Error)	599662	40600	14.77		
Total	613529	40614			

will give a lower P value, the value $p < 0.05$ in Table (4.3) indicates that the mean TCO distributions over different longitudinal bands have a significant difference. This means that we obtained enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. We have carried out a multiple comparison technique to investigate the difference among TCO measurements at different longitude bands as shown in Table (4.4).

TABLE 4.4: Longitudinal statistical variations of TCO measurements

Lon($^{\circ}$)	Lon($^{\circ}$)	Lower Limits	$\mu_1 - \mu_2$	Upper Limits	p-value
42.5	47.5	1.733	1.85	1.967	0.150
42.5	46.5	-0.901	0.22	1.338	1.000
42.5	45.5	-0.554	0.57	1.687	0.930
42.5	44.5	-1.219	-0.10	1.020	1.000
42.5	43.5	-1.35	-0.23	0.890	1.000
42.5	41.5	-1.537	-0.42	0.703	0.996
42.5	40.5	-0.356	0.36	1.073	0.895
39.5	38.5	-0.782	0.34	1.458	0.990
39.5	37.5	-0.200	0.92	2.04	0.255
39.5	36.5	-2.021	-0.90	0.219	0.287
39.5	35.5	-0.510	0.61	1.73	0.880
39.5	34.5	-1.744	0.62	0.496	0.859
39.5	33.5	-1.159	0.04	1.081	1.000

We can see from Table (4.4) that the study area can be divided into two sub-regions based on the characteristics of TCO measurements as Western cluster covering the regions from $33.5^{\circ}E$ to $39.5^{\circ}E$ and Eastern cluster covering the region $40.5^{\circ}E$ to $47.5^{\circ}E$. A similar procedure follows for the latitudinal clustering as discussed below.

4.5.2 Latitudinal Clustering

Following the null hypothesis defined in the previous subsection but for latitudinal bands, we have carried out a similar investigation in order to cluster TCO measurements at different latitude bands.

Similar to the longitudinal clustering the value $p \leq 0.05$ in Table (4.5) shows that the average TCO measurements along different latitudinal bands differ significantly and this means that our null hypothesis is rejected. In Table (4.5) again, the total degree of freedom is 32557 due to the missing data values in C_{lat} Equation (4.1) that can't be replaced with linear interpolation. We have carried out multiple comparison technique to study the level of statistical difference among TCO measurements over different latitudinal bands as shown in Table (4.6).

TABLE 4.5: Standard Analysis of Variance Table for latitudinal bands (C_{lat}) (Eqn 4.1, $k=12$, $N=2890 \times 12$). Results demonstrate mean difference among the latitudinal bands

Source of Variation	Sum square	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares	F	P
Between bands (Groups)	5886.1	11	535.1	33.26	0.00001
Within bands (Error)	523670	32546	16.09		
Total	529556	32557			

TABLE 4.6: Latitudinal statistical variations of TCO measurements

Lat($^{\circ}$)	Lat($^{\circ}$)	Lower Limits	$\mu_1 - \mu_2$	Upper Limits	p-value
13.5	14.5	0.4394	0.50	0.5526	0.9606
13.5	12.5	-0.0831	1.06	2.2057	0.0997
13.5	11.5	-1.7109	-0.57	0.5772	0.9025
13.5	10.5	-1.9826	-0.84	0.3055	0.4090
13.5	9.5	-2.1184	-0.97	0.1690	0.1862
6.5	8.5	-1.9065	-0.76	0.3810	0.5647
6.5	7.5	-1.4069	-0.26	0.8805	0.9998
6.5	5.5	-2.0219	-0.88	0.2658	0.3342
6.5	4.5	-2.0874	-0.94	0.2007	0.2286
6.5	3.5	-0.21	0.86	1.9300	0.0171

Table (4.6) depicts results of the multiple comparisons analysis. The comparisons clearly show that the study area can be divided into two sub-regions based on the statistical difference of the TCO measurements over different latitude as Southern region covering 4.5° to $8.5^{\circ}N$ and Northern region that covers 9.5° to $14.5^{\circ}N$. Here, the sample mean TCO value of $3.5^{\circ}N$ has a significant difference value from its nearest values (eg. for $6.5^{\circ}N - 3.5^{\circ}N$; the p-value is $p < 0.05$), which means they are not grouped in the same cluster. On the other hand, Table 4.1 (for $14.5^{\circ}N - 3.5^{\circ}N$ the value of $R^2 < 0.8$) indicates that the sample mean value at $3.5^{\circ}N$ cannot be expressed by the northernmost values. Hence, based on this analysis the band $3.5^{\circ}N$ was supposed to be a separate additional cluster, however, as indicated in Figure 4.1, the number of data points at 3.5° are only two, and both are at the boundary which means these are too small in number to be considered as a separate visible cluster as we are

considering Ethiopia only in the map. Of course, this may indicate that if we were considering a region larger than Ethiopia we would have at least one more cluster that include $3.5^{\circ}N$ band.

4.5.3 Multiple Clustering

The discussions in the previous subsections on latitudinal and longitudinal clusters reveals the existence of two clusters for each latitudinal and longitudinal bands as Northern and Southern clusters for latitudinal bands, and Eastern and western clusters for longitudinal bands. It is useful to study if a given cluster itself can be represented by another cluster as the classifications above have been done by considering one dimension and that is through the latitudinal or longitudinal bands separately. Classification through two-dimensional space allows proper mapping of TCO for practical application. We consider NW, NE, SW and SE regions for multiple clustering. Classification of clusters can be studied by means of multiple clustering methods following the approach by (Boulis and Ostendorf, 2004). The statistical parameters obtained by multiple clustering analysis of the clusters are presented in Table (4.7).

TABLE 4.7: Statistical parameters obtained by multiple clustering.

Groups	Groups	Lower Limits	$\mu_1 - \mu_2$	Upper Limits	p-value
NW	NE	2.3599	3.2441	4.1243	0.0001
NW	SW	5.6625	6.5446	7.4267	0.0002
NW	SE	6.1906	7.0728	9.9549	0.001
NE	SW	2.4203	3.3025	4.1847	0.0004
NE	SE	2.9485	3.8307	4.7129	0.001
SW	SE	-0.3539	0.5282	1.4103	0.4145

In Table (4.7) the lower p-values ($p < 0.05$) indicate that the mean TCO distributions over different sub-regions have a significant difference. However, the p-value in the last column ($P > 0.05$) demonstrates that there is no significant difference between the mean of South-Western and South-Eastern clusters. This means that we found that there is only three clusters of the mean TCO distributions over Ethiopia. These are North-Western, North-Eastern and Southern clusters. The result is confirmed by

Calinski-Harabasz criterion for Optimal number of clusters as indicated in Figure (4.9)

FIGURE 4.9: Optimal number of clusters

The larger the VRCK ratio, the better the data partition. To determine the optimal number of clusters, maximize VRCK with respect to k (Firuzi *et al.*, 2017). The optimal number of clusters corresponds to the solution with the highest Calinski-Harabasz index value. As indicated in Figure 4.9, the Calinski-Harabasz criterion values were tested for each number of clusters. The result shows that the highest value of Calinski-Harabasz indicates that the optimum number of clusters is three. We note we applied the internal cluster validation method to measure the quality of the clustering because there is no ground data. Therefore, it is a reliable model.

4.6 TEMPORAL TCO DISTRIBUTION

In order to analyze the temporal characteristics of TCO over the three clusters, we assess the mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation and extreme values of TCO is given in Table (4.8). Table (4.8) shows that the mean TCO concentration was 264.29DU, 261.0DU and 258.73DU over North-Western, North-Eastern, Southern clusters respectively. Moreover, the overall sample mean TCO of Ethiopia was found

TABLE 4.8: Mean, Standard Deviation and Coefficient of variation over all clusters

Region	Mean			Minimum TCO(DU)	Maximum TCO(DU)
	TCO(DU)	std	CV%		
NW	264.29	13.6	5.15	217	301
NE	261.0	13.73	5.26	217	298
SO	258.73	11.28	4.36	216	299
ETH	261.35	12.62	1.07	216	301

to be 261.35DU. Table (4.8) and the raw data showed that the TCO concentration has a maximum value of 301DU during summer on August 18, 2013 and a minimum value of 216DU during winter on January 03, 2013 over the study period. The concentration of TCO clearly shows increasing values with latitudinal changes from South to North which is consistent with the previous studies carried out in other regions (London, 1985; Krueger, 1989; Rafiq *et al.*, 2017).

4.6.1 Temporal TCO Distribution on Seasons

Total column ozone varies with seasons and latitudes for the study period. Detailed study has been made to understand the temporal variability of TCO over each clusters as shown in Table (4.9)

TABLE 4.9: Mean TCO Concentration on Seasons

	NWC	NEC	SOC
Winter	250.28	246.73	247.98
Spring	272.39	268.94	263.26
Summer	276.26	273.31	269.08
Autumn	257.43	254.34	253.97

The seasonally averaged TCO values are shown in Table (4.9). The summer season has recorded the greatest mean TCO value in all clusters, whereas the winter season has the lowest ozone concentration. On the other hand, the mean TCO concentration over NWC is highest across all seasons, whereas it is lowest over SOC.

Figures (4.10, 4.11 and 4.12), show the raw data and the trend of TCO over each clusters.

FIGURE 4.10: TCO distribution of NWC during a) Winter, b) spring C) Summer & d) Autumn Seasons

FIGURE 4.11: TCO distribution of NEC during a) Winter, b) spring C) Summer & d) Autumn Seasons

Figures (4.10, 4.11 and 4.12) show that overall column ozone concentrations increase across all three clusters during the winter season while decreasing across

FIGURE 4.12: TCO distribution of SOC during a) Winter, b) spring C) Summer & d) Autumn Seasons

all three clusters during the other seasons. It shows also on figure (4.4 & 4.5) as a minimum total column ozone concentration during December, January and February months, may be attributed to several factors one of the major factor may be the solar irradiance reaching the Earth's surface decreases due to the tilt of the Earth's axis. Reduced solar radiation means reduced photochemical ozone production, leading to lower ozone concentrations. The other might be Stratospheric Dynamics: The polar cell circulation and the stratospheric polar night jet play important roles in redistributing ozone within the stratosphere. During winter, these dynamics can lead to the accumulation of ozone at higher latitudes, resulting in decreased ozone concentrations at lower latitudes such as Ethiopia. The stratospheric temperature decreases and polar vortex might be also the major factors as the stratospheric temperature decreases leading to enhanced ozone production and reduced ozone destruction. The lower temperatures also favor the formation of polar stratospheric clouds which can contribute to additional ozone depletion. The polar vortex, which is a large-scale circulation pattern in the stratosphere, becomes more stable over the polar regions. This leads to the accumulation of ozone-rich air within the vortex, causing increased

column ozone concentrations.

These factors collectively contribute to the observed lowest concentration occurring in the December-February period. It is important to note that these are general trends and can vary based on specific atmospheric and climatic conditions in different years. Local and regional factors may also influence the ozone levels in specific areas within Ethiopia.

4.6.2 Timeseries Analysis

We investigated the seasonal nature and trend of ozone distributions through time-series analysis. This is carried out by decomposing the daily timeseries data into trends, seasonal variations, and residual components for each cluster regions independently. The time-series data can be modeled as an additive form due to its similar seasonal effect in each year (Dodge and Commenges, 2006).

The trend of the TCO variations cannot be identified easily because of the seasonal cyclic variations (Antón *et al.*, 2011). In this study we have detected the period of seasonal pattern by using two different techniques. Visual inspection of timeseries plot as indicated on Figure 4.13 can be considered as one option.

FIGURE 4.13: Monthly Mean TCO over clusters

From the sequences of timeseries data plots in Figure 4.13, the concentration over all of the sub-regions was highest during June, July, and August. It also shows the concentration decreases until December and then rises continuously to July, and hence the annual cyclic behavior is observed. On the other hand, the seasonality of TCO is estimated from the best fit of daily TCO timeseries ((Fioletov *et al.*, 2008; Antón *et al.*, 2011)). We also estimated the cyclic variability of TCO by best fitting of measured data through Fourier series model given by equation 4.12. In order to identify the dominant frequencies of a timeseries, we used a power spectrum Fast Fourier Transform on our measured data which is given in terms of frequency instead of period as indicated in Figure 4.14.

FIGURE 4.14: spectral periodogram a)NWC, b) NEC & c) SOC of Ethiopia

The spectral periodogram plot shows that there is a single Fourier power peak with the corresponding frequency $f = 0.002768\text{Hz}$ for all clusters. The inverse of this frequency, which is period of the annual cyclic behavior, is 365.25 days. This result is in line with the previous studies by (Fioletov *et al.*, 2008; Antón *et al.*, 2011; Chen *et al.*, 2014; Vigouroux *et al.*, 2015).

TABLE 4.10: Tests of goodness of fit for seasonal components

Cluster		Fourier terms(n)	
		n = 1	n = 2
NW	R^2	0.7865	0.8090
	RMSE	6.2338	5.9002
NE	R^2	0.7959	0.8146
	RMSE	6.1597	5.8741
SO	R^2	0.6835	0.7007
	RMSE	6.3229	6.1536

Table 4.10 shows that for a Fourier term $n = 1$: the coefficients of determination (R^2) are 0.7865, 0.7959, and 0.6835 for North-Western, North-Eastern, and Southern clusters respectively. In North-Western and North-Eastern clusters the coefficient of determination (R^2) is higher than 0.7 and it is considered as a good seasonal fit Akoglu (2018). However, the coefficient of determination (R^2) for the Southern cluster was lower than 0.7 and its coefficient of determination (R^2) for $n=2$ is higher than 0.70. In this case, we used $n=1$ for North-Western & North-Eastern clusters while $n=2$ for the Southern cluster.

The equations for the seasonality component becomes $S_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \cos(\frac{2\pi t}{365.25}) + \beta_1 \sin(\frac{2\pi t}{365.25})$ for North-Western & North-Eastern clusters and

$S_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \cos(\frac{2\pi t}{365.25}) + \beta_1 \sin(\frac{2\pi t}{365.25}) + \alpha_2 \cos(\frac{4\pi t}{365.25}) + \beta_2 \sin(\frac{4\pi t}{365.25})$, for Southern cluster. The estimated parameters are presented in Table 4.11.

Table 4.10 shows that we have a Fourier transform term of $n = 1$ for North-Western & North-Eastern clusters while $n = 2$ for the Southern cluster. In this case, the coefficients of the fitting functions indicated in Table 4.11 have a coefficient of

TABLE 4.11: Parameter Estimation for seasonal components

Cluster	Estimates			
	α_1	β_1	α_2	β_2
NW	-16.85	3.843		
NE	-16.56	3.852		
SO	-13.14	1.616	-1.344	1.512

determination (R^2) of 0.7865, 0.7959, and 0.7007 for North-Western, North-Eastern and Southern clusters respectively. Moreover, the seasonal component is the best fit of measured data as indicated in Figure (4.15).

FIGURE 4.15: the seasonal components over a) North-Western, b) North-Eastern & c) Southern clusters of Ethiopia

In order to assess the long term monotonic trend, first we have defined a 5% threshold with null hypothesis as there is no monotonic trend and we have applied non-parametric Mann-Kendall trend test.

The P-value of < 0.05 in Table (4.12) indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis H_0 : and it reveals the existence of monotonic trend over all the three clusters. The long term increasing or decreasing pattern of TCO timeseries have been modeled using linear trend in Africa (Oluleye and Okogbue, 2013). In this study as well, we assumed a linear trend defined by equation 4.17. The average daily deseasonalized

TABLE 4.12: Mann-Kendall trend test result over the three clusters daily data

	Clusters		
	NWC	NEC	SOC
N	2890	2890	2890
S-val	-422952	-401190	-230736
Z-stat	-8.1649	-7.7448	-4.4543
P-val	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001

data and the corresponding linear fitted line is summarized as follows.

FIGURE 4.16: Deseasonalized timeseries data with a fitted line over a) North-Western, b) North-Eastern & c) Southern clusters of Ethiopia

We obtained the linear trend equations corresponding to each cluster TCO timeseries as $y_{nw} = -0.0021x + 3.066$, $y_{ne} = -0.00201x + 3$, and $y_s = -0.0012x + 2.079$ for monthly ozone concentration over the North-Western, North-Eastern and Southern clusters of Ethiopia, respectively. We have given in Figure (4.16) deseasonalized timeseries plots together with the fitted trends for each cluster. To strengthen the current study, as the serial correlated residual in Figure (4.16) show that runs of high and low values tend to persist for a few months, and to see the robustness of the trend even in the presence of serial correlation, we implement the Mann-Kendall test on the deseasonalized timeseries averaged into DJF-MAM-JJA-SON (3-month means

for each year). We have given in Table 4.13 Mann-Kendall trend test result for the deseasonalized three months mean timeseries for illustration purpose.

TABLE 4.13: The three months mean deseasonalized data Mann-Kendall trend test result for the three clusters

	Clusters		
	NWC	NEC	SOC
N	32	32	32
S-val	-142	-138	-82
Z-stat	-2.287	-2.221	-1.313
P-val	0.022	0.026	0.189

The P-value of < 0.05 in Table (4.13) indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis and the test result reveals again the existence of similar monotonic trend for Northwest and Northeast clusters timeseries. However, for the southern cluster the Mann-Kendall test shows no significant trend which might be due the structural noise is a bit higher than the corresponding trend in this cluster which shows the impact of significant serial correlation on trend estimates.

FIGURE 4.17: The three months mean deseasonalized data over a)NWC b) NEC & c) SOC

For the model predictive performance evaluation, we use two sets of performance metrics, namely residual diagnostics and autocorrelation tests. The objective is to determine whether the residuals of the models resemble white noise or not. Figure 4.18, 4.19 and 4.20 showed different residual plots and the autocorrelation plot of the model, the top panels showed the residuals plot of the temporally correlated noises ε_t with seasonal variances in the model, the middle panels showed that the plot of residuals v_t from which the correlation is removed in the block AR model. The bottom panels shows the plot of the standardized residuals $v_t/\hat{\sigma}_t$, using the fitted standard deviation, which exactly resembles white noise, as expected with unit variance.

FIGURE 4.18: Residual plots over NWC a) Correlated Noises with non constant Variance b) Correlation Removed Residual & c) standardized residuals

The autocorrelation plot of the standardized residuals $v_t/\hat{\sigma}_t$ in Figure 4.21, also suggests that the residuals are almost normally distributed and are Gaussian noises. The estimated parameters for residual components of each of the three clusters are presented in Table 4.14

In Figure (4.22), we give TCO plot with two-sigma model output confidence interval to indicate the model's accuracy. This helped us quantify the uncertainty of the sample estimates for the entire TCO time series. As the range is narrow, the margin of error is small and it is a range of plausible values which shows the model's output is

FIGURE 4.19: Residual plots over NEC a) Correlated Noises with non constant Variance b) Correlation Removed Residual & c) standardized residuals

FIGURE 4.20: Residual plots over SOC a) Correlated Noises with non constant Variance b) Correlation Removed Residual & c) standardized residuals

a reasonable estimate. we have checked the overall model performance by computing the R^2 between the model output and the time series data. We obtained R^2 values of 0.85, 0.86, 0.79 for NWC, NEC and SOC respectively and the result indicates the overall goodness of fit of the model is reasonably good. In order to evaluate the reliability of these models in describing the data, we also investigate the residuals of the models if

FIGURE 4.21: ACF plot over a) North-Western, b) North-Eastern & c) Southern clusters of Ethiopia

TABLE 4.14: Parameter Estimation for Residual components

Cluster	Estimates		
	ϕ_1	ϕ_2	ϕ_3
NWC	0.8212	-0.0503	0.0933
NEC	0.8591	-0.0558	-0.0922
SOC	0.9375	-0.1205	0.1351

they resemble white noise.

The normal probability quantile-quantile plot of the standardized residual given in Figure (4.23) shows that the residuals can be regarded as Gaussian noise without any signs of large outliers and hence the proposed time series model is reliable for this set of data. In general, based on this study and the results of other researchers over Kenya, West Africa, and Pakistan (Oluleye and Okogbue, 2013; Madhu *et al.*, 2016; Rafiq *et al.*, 2017; Songa, 2017), the source of seasonal variability of ozone distribution over Ethiopia may be mainly due to ozone transport and chemistry. However, in

FIGURE 4.22: The Confidence interval of the model a) Northwestern, b) Northeastern & c) Southern clusters of Ethiopia

FIGURE 4.23: QQ plot for Remaining Components a) Northwestern, b) Northeastern & c) Southern clusters of Ethiopia

order to reach a more strong conclusion, the impact of Quasi-Biennial Oscillation (QBO) and Solar UV radiation on the variability of ozone over Ethiopia should be

studied in detail.

4.7 CONCLUSION

We have studied the spatial distribution of total column ozone concentration over Ethiopia using OMPS- NM satellite daily data from 108 data points over Ethiopia for the period of 2012-2019. The study has shown that the maximum total column ozone concentration occurred during the summer seasons, while the minimum measurements were recorded during the winter seasons in North-Western and Central Ethiopia. The annual mean total column ozone concentration during the study period is found to be (261.35 ± 2.38) DU. The maximum total column ozone of 301 DU was observed on 18 August 2013 while the minimum of 216 DU was measured on January 03, 2013.

We have also showed through spatial data clustering study that that the spatial distribution of the total column ozone concentration over Ethiopia can be classified into three major representative clusters: Southern Cluster ($4.5^{\circ}N$ to $8.5^{\circ}N$ & $33.5^{\circ}E$ – $47.5^{\circ}E$), North-Eastern Cluster ($9.5^{\circ}N$ to $14.5^{\circ}N$ & $41.5^{\circ}E$ to $47.5^{\circ}E$) and North-Western Cluster ($9.5^{\circ}N$ to $14.5^{\circ}N$ & $33.5^{\circ}E$ to $40.5^{\circ}E$). The TCO timeseries analysis has shown a decreasing linear trend in TCO with a depletion rate of 0.77 DU/yr, 0.73 DU/yr, and 0.43 DU/yr over North-Western, North-Eastern & Southern clusters of Ethiopia respectively. We also found a single power peak with the frequency of $f = 0.002768Hz$ with an annual cyclic behavior for the three clusters. The analysis of residuals for each cluster indicated that the residuals are normally distributed with no significant outliers and the model explains 85% ,86% and 79% of the variance in the North-West, North-East and Southern clusters respectively, demonstrating the reliability of the model considered in this study.

CHAPTER 5

PERFORMANCES OF SURFACE OZONE LEVEL FORECASTING MODELS
IN ETHIOPIA

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5.1 INTRODUCTION

Tropospheric ozone level (TOL) also known as surface-level ozone and tropospheric ozone becomes one of the critical concerns over the world. A high level of surface ozone concentrations can damage the human respiratory system, organs, immune systems & tissues, and even sometimes threaten human life as a major air pollutant (Adams, 1987; Jerrett *et al.*, 2009; Anenberg *et al.*, 2010; McGrath *et al.*, 2015; Wang *et al.*, 2017). It also affects the growth of plants by destroying their leaf tissues (Chameides *et al.*, 1994; Cao *et al.*, 2012; Feng *et al.*, 2015; Lefohn *et al.*, 2017). In addition to this, ozone is an important greenhouse gas as it protects the Earth from dangerous UV rays from the Sun. Ozone affects climate change, which in turn the climate change influences ozone concentration through chemical composition, transport, and temperature changes (Chattopadhyay and Chattopadhyay, 2010a).

Moreover, it is a harmful air pollutant and the air quality index tracks TOL as one of the major air pollutants. The United States Environmental Protection Agency revised the National Ambient Air Quality Standard for ozone On October 1, 2015, from 0.075 parts per million (ppm) to 0.070 ppm, averaged over 8 hours. Hence, it requires a real-time climate prediction of O_3 to design future policies on control strategies of O_3 that could support planning for air pollution control (Anenberg *et al.*,

2010; Wang *et al.*, 2017).

Accurate modeling of O_3 is important to ensure its exact prediction. Efficient prediction of TOL is becoming a necessity for preventing the highly challenging events related to the peak concentration of ozone. Many prediction models use a statistical method as a tool for forecasting future data. In statistical data analysis, there are several methods for statistical prediction, such as regressing analysis, classical decomposition method, Box and Jenkins method, and smoothing techniques. Various statistical methods will give different predictions depending on the range of data sets. These techniques provide predicting models of different accuracy.

In natural situations, the concentration of ozone in any area has a lot of seasonality and trends (Cros *et al.*, 1988; Zou, 1996; Carslaw, 2005; Alemu *et al.*, 2022). Forecasting such cases requires models which will account for the trend and seasonality in the data. One of the most widely applied forecasting techniques that is used to project future values is Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model, which is a more generalization of ARMA model. The basic assumptions in implementing the ARMA model is the stationarity of the data series. The model combines two different components: Auto-regression (AR) and Moving average (MA). The AR part indicates a changing variable that regresses on its prior value; the MA part indicates the dependency between the observation & a residual error. However, in reality the ozone series may not be stationary always to be best modeled with ARMA.

On the other hand, ARIMA model is useful to model non-stationarity time series. It assumes that the data becomes stationary after differencing, and the Integral (I) part represents the differencing of raw observations to allow for the time series to become stationary. Moreover, for seasonal time series forecasting, scholars in the field proposed a Seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA) model (Box, 1976). For instance, Guarnaccia *et al.* (2018) implemented ARIMA to predict air pollution in San Nicolas de Garza of Monterrey in Mexico. They used hourly Carbon-monoxide concentrations data to estimate ARIMA model parameters and predict future pollution. Their study

indicated that the ARIMA model yields reliable prediction on a short time range up to 24 hours in the future with a reasonable compromise between precision and the forecast horizon from the hourly data. Kumar *et al.* (2004) also used ARIMA model to obtain maximum daily surface ozone concentration forecasts from hourly surface-level ozone data collected in the period July 1998–March 1999 at the airport in Brunei Darussalam. Their study revealed that the overall model performance was found to be quite satisfactory with Normalized Mean Square Error of 0.02 and Mean Absolute Percentage Error of 13.14 % . Gocheva-Ilieva *et al.* (2014) also investigated future concentrations of primary air pollutants including ground level ozone in the town of Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria within a 1 year period from 1st September 2011 to 31st August 2012, based on hourly measurements. Their study indicated that the SARIMA models obtained demonstrated very good fitting performance with regard to the observed air pollutants and short-term predictions for 72 h ahead, in particular in the case of ozone.

Similarly, Holt–Winters’ modeling is the other most common time series prediction method that can take into account both the trend and seasonality in the forecasting. It is useful to model the three different components of a time series (i.e. the average or level, trend and seasonality components of a series). Hence, Holt–Winters model comprises the level, trend and seasonality components of a time series together with corresponding parameters called smoothing parameters. In statistical modeling, the models are formulated using a training data sets for estimating model parameters in such a way that the model best fits the training data sets so that one can use the model to predict future values of the series. In this case, one of the model’s predictive performance is usually evaluated using test data sets by implementing different measurement metrics such as RMSE, MAE & MAPE.

Both ARIMA and Holt–Winters models are commonly used in time series analysis in general. To mention some, (Syafei *et al.*, 2018) implemented both Holt-Winters and ARIMA to predict the concentrations of daily air pollutants in Surabaya, Indonesia from a 15 days hourly air quality data in 2014 such as particulate (PM₁₀), carbon monoxide (CO), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and ozone (O₃)

concentrations. Their finding showed that Holt-Winters model performed well in forecasting CO, NO₂ and O₃, where as ARIMA is best in forecasting PH₁₀ and SO₂. In a study conducted by (Alonso Brito *et al.*, 2021), SARIMA model presented better results than Holt-Winters in forecasting monthly streamflow. On the other hand, (Omara and Kawamukaia, 2021) in a study about the prediction of Normalized Difference Vegetation Index, obtained better results by the Holt Winters' method. Moreover, Markovska *et al.* (2016) showed that the ARIMA model gives more accurate results when the prediction is based on daily time-series data, while the Holt-Winters model has better performance for weekly and monthly time series data. Thus, the studies so far indicated that both ARIMA and Holt-Winters models are applicable to forecast future values in time series data in general but, there is no general consensus regarding which model is better for which time series data and in what scenario explicitly. It is reasonable to assume from the previous studies that the models performance depends on specific time series data under study. This and literature search insights of null report in the area of ground-level ozone forecast in the Ethiopian context motivated us to investigate ARIMA and Holt-Winters models forecast of ground-level ozone of four selected stations of Ethiopia.

In this study, we modeled the ground-level ozone series of four selected stations (Addis Ababa, Bahir Dar, Ras Dashen and Danakil Depression) of Ethiopia during the study period by considering trends and seasonality patterns from ECMWF monthly ground-level ozone data. Particularly, our concern is on seasonal ARIMA and Holt-Winters model forecasts together with corresponding model performance.

The remaining part of this section is organized as follows: In Subsection 2, we discuss the geographical location of the study area. Subsection 3 provides information on data description and methodology. Subsection 4 contains the results and discussions of the study. Finally, the conclusions of the study are forwarded.

5.2 STUDY AREA

North-Western cluster of Ethiopia is found in the North-Eastern part of Africa, which lies approximately between $9.5^{\circ}N$ & $14.5^{\circ}N$ latitude and $32.5^{\circ}E$ & $40.5^{\circ}E$ longitude. We are interested to investigate the concentration of TOL over the North-Western cluster of Ethiopia. The motivation for this specific study area in Ethiopia arises from a study report by (Alemu *et al.*, 2022) that indicates the existence of a high overall mean TCO concentration over the North-Western part of Ethiopia and a low concentration over the Southern part of Ethiopia. We would like to see the ground-level ozone time series contributions to the high level of overall mean TCO in the study area bearing in mind that low TOL and high TCO are useful to life on Earth.

The topography of the study area considered is highly diverse, including the extreme points of Ethiopia, with an elevation ranging from -125 m at the Danakil Depression which is the hottest place on earth to 4620 m at Ras-Dashen mountain (Judith, 1991; Habtegebreal and Alemu, 2019). These variations in topography might also have an impact on the distribution of surface level ozone and its forecast. The objective is thus to model the status of surface level ozone over the selected four stations: Addis Ababa (AA), Ras Dashen (RD), Danakil Depression (DD), and Bahir Dar (BD) as shown in Figure 4.1 (corresponding topographic details are given in Table. 5.1), and to forecast it with corresponding model performance check.

TABLE 5.1: Geographical Location and Elevation of Stations

Station Code	Longtiude ($^{\circ}$)	Latitiude ($^{\circ}$)	altitude
AA	38.74	9.03	2355
RD	38.37	13.24	4550
DK	40.30	14.24	-125
BD	37.36	11.57	1800

5.3 DATA DESCRIPTION AND METHODOLOGY

In this work we utilized TOL data from European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) from November 2007 – December 2020. We split the data into two parts: the first part of data (November 2007– December 2019) is used for model formulation & parameter estimation and the last year's data (January 1, 2020 – December 31, 2020) is used for model validation.

We have applied the SARIMA Modeling and Holt winter's modeling for comparing the performance of forecasting monthly TOL over the selected locations of Ethiopia. Both types of modeling techniques are presented separately as follow

5.3.1 *Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA) Modeling*

Forecasting is a time-series projection of future events based on current and historical data (Montgomery *et al.*, 2015). For time series data, there are several different prediction methods. Among the effective approaches for analyzing time series data, ARIMA modeling is one of the most widely used methods for data with both seasonal patterns and trends. ARIMA model has been used to forecast the mid and Long-term concentration of ozone over many study areas (Chattopadhyay and Chattopadhyay, 2010b; Mahiyuddin *et al.*, 2018; Li *et al.*, 2021).

ARIMA model can be thought as a model that combines three different time series models: AR, I and MA models. The AR part of ARIMA indicates the change of a variable that regresses on some of its prior values, the MA part indicates the dependency between an observation and a residual error and the I part represents the differencing of raw observations to allow for the time series to become stationary. ARIMA models can be denoted by $ARIMA(p,d,q)$, where p is the order of time lag of the autoregressive model, d is the degree of differencing and q is the order of the moving average model.

An autoregressive model of order p is the one in which the current observation x_t is regressed on previous observations $x_{t-1}, x_{t-2}, \dots, x_{t-p}$ of the same time series. This can be expressed mathematically as

$$x_t = \zeta + \phi_1 x_{t-1} + \phi_2 x_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p x_{t-p} + \epsilon_t, \quad (5.1)$$

where, $\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_p$ represents the regression coefficients, ζ is the constant term, and ϵ_t is the random error. Taking the ϕ terms to the left hand side reduces Equation (5.1) in to

$$x_t - \phi_1 x_{t-1} - \phi_2 x_{t-2} - \dots - \phi_p x_{t-p} = \zeta + \epsilon_t,$$

If B denotes the backward shift operator such that $Bx_t = x_{t-1}$, $Bx_{t-1} = x_{t-2}$, and so on, Equation 5.1 can be written as

$$(1 - \phi_1 B - \phi_2 B^2 - \dots - \phi_p B^p)x_t = \zeta + \epsilon_t, \quad (5.2)$$

Replacing x_t by its deviation (\bar{x}_t) from the mean μ , the equation becomes

$$\phi_p(B)\bar{x}_t = \epsilon_t, \quad (5.3)$$

where, $\phi_p(B) = 1 - \phi_1 B - \phi_2 B^2 - \dots - \phi_p B^p$, and $\bar{x}_t = x_t - \mu$

Similarly, a moving average model of order q can be defined in terms of the random error terms as

$$x_t = \mu + \epsilon_t - \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} - \theta_2 \epsilon_{t-2} - \dots - \theta_q \epsilon_{t-q} \quad (5.4)$$

In terms of the backward shift operator B , a moving average model of order q can be expressed as

$$x_t = \mu + (1 - \theta_1 B - \theta_2 B^2 - \dots - \theta_q B^q)\epsilon_t \quad (5.5)$$

or

$$x_t = \mu + \theta_q(B)\epsilon_t,$$

where, $\theta_q(B) = 1 - \theta_1 B - \theta_2 B^2 - \dots - \theta_q B^q$

The two models AR(p) and MA(q) can be combined to form a mixed Autoregressive Moving Average model ARMA(p,q) for a stationary time series that is represented by Equation (5.7)

$$\phi_p(B)x_t = \zeta + \theta_q(B)q_t \quad (5.6)$$

$$y_t = \zeta + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=0}^q \theta_j \epsilon_{t-j}, \quad (5.7)$$

where, y_t is the observed Ground-level ozone value at time t, ζ is a constant, i and j are the autoregressive and moving average process lags respectively, ϕ_i is the autoregressive coefficient at lag i , θ_j is the moving average coefficient at lag j , p and q are the autoregressive and moving average orders respectively.

These models are applicable to a stationary time series. If the time series is non-stationary, it needs first to be transformed into a stationary time series by a process called differencing, in which the previous observation x_{t-1} is subtracted from the current observation x_t . The differencing can be performed with the help of a difference operator ∇ defined as

$$\nabla^d x_t = \nabla(\nabla^{d-1} x_t), \quad (5.8)$$

Combining the three techniques (autoregressive model, moving average model, and differencing), an ARIMA model is generated. A general ARIMA model of order (p, d, q) representing a time series can be expressed as

$$\phi(B) \nabla^d x_t = \theta(B)q_t \quad (5.9)$$

In the context of the present study, x_t and q_t represent the surface ozone level and random error terms at time t, respectively, while d represents the order of differencing.

SARIMA is an extension of ARIMA that includes additional seasonal term. Seasonality can be defined as a pattern of repeating itself over a fixed time interval (Taneja *et al.*, 2016). In addition to ARIMA, there will be four additional elements in SARIMA that corresponds to orders corresponding to the seasonal elements. The TOL can be modeled using SARIMA model with order $(p,d,q)(P,D,Q)[s]$, where P, D and Q are order of seasonal AR polynomial function, order of seasonal MA polynomial function and order of seasonal differencing respectively for period of the season s. The general equation can be written as shown in Equation (5.10) (Martinez *et al.*, 2011).

$$\Phi(L^s)\phi(L)(1-L)^d(1-L^s)^D y_t = \Theta(L^s)\theta(L)\epsilon_t, \quad (5.10)$$

where L is the lag operator, $\phi(L)$ is the autoregressive polynomial function of order p, $\theta(L)$ is the moving average polynomial function of order q, $\Phi(L^s)$ is the seasonal autoregressive polynomial function of order P, $\Theta(L^s)$ is the seasonal moving average polynomial function of order Q, d is the differencing order, D is the seasonal differencing order and ϵ_t must be normally distributed, not autocorrelated & homoscedastic error term.

5.3.2 Holt-Winters Modeling

Holt-Winters modeling is also the most widely used method for time series data with both trend and seasonal patterns. The method comprises of forecast and smoothing equations for level, trend, and seasonal components with corresponding smoothing parameters α , β , and γ , respectively. It is a method of forecasting that applies exponential smoothing technique to the seasonal component in addition to the level and trends (Lawton, 1998; Bermúdez *et al.*, 2006). Due to its accuracy in prediction, Holt-Winters model has been widely used in many fields.(Dantas *et al.*, 2017) used Holt-Winters method to forecast air transportation demand. (Reizer and Juda-Rezler, 2016) also used Holt-Winters model to forecast the daily PM2.5 concentrations.

For the additive Holt-Winters prediction function the level equation is given by the weighted average between the seasonally adjusted observation and non-seasonal

forecast for time t.

$$L_t = \alpha(y_t - S_{t-s}) + (1 - \alpha)(L_{t-1} + T_{t-1}) \quad (5.11)$$

The trend equation is given by the weighted average of the estimated trends at time t based on $L_t - L_{t-1}$ and T_{t-1} , the previous estimates of the trend.

$$T_t = \beta(L_t - L_{t-1}) + (1 - \beta)T_{t-1} \quad (5.12)$$

The seasonal equation is given by the weighted average between the current seasonal index and the seasonal index of the same season s period ago.

$$S_t = \gamma(y_t - L_t) + (1 - \gamma)S_{t-s} \quad (5.13)$$

The forecast equation is given by

$$F_{t+k} = L_t + kT_t + S_{t+k-s}, \quad (5.14)$$

where s is the length of the seasonal cycle for the parameters (α , β and γ) are restricted to the range from 0 to 1.

The time series data are also grouped into two sections: the initial data and testing data. The initial data are the data of two seasonal periods. The initial data are used to obtain the initial value of the base level, trends and seasonal factors. While the test data are used to make the process of forecasting with the number of data p . In the test data, the values of the base level, trend, and seasonal factors are calculated for each period. Initial value for the base level is given by

$$L_0 = \frac{1}{h} \sum_{i=0}^h X_i, \quad (5.15)$$

where h is the number of initial data and X_i for $i=1,2,\dots,h$ are the initial data. Initial value for the trend (T_0) is given by

$$T_0 = \frac{\bar{X}_{t2} - \bar{X}_{t1}}{m}, \quad (5.16)$$

where \bar{X}_{t1} is the average of the initial year data, \bar{X}_{t2} is the average of second year data, and m is the number of seasons used in forecasting. We use R software for model selection and multistep ahead point forecast.

5.3.3 Model performance

Goodness of fit is the measure of model accuracy with respect to the observed values or data. We have used AIC and BIC to compare the accuracy of models in the same class of ARIMA models which estimates the relative amount of information lost by a given model under the assumption of independent model errors. In the current study, we used both AIC and BIC to assess the degree of accuracy of the forecasts as proposed by (Akaike, 1998). We define AIC and BIC as follows.

$$AIC = \ln(\sigma_\epsilon^2) + \frac{2(p+q)}{n}, \quad (5.17)$$

$$BIC = n \ln \sigma_\epsilon^2 + k \ln(n), \quad (5.18)$$

$$\sigma_\epsilon^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i^o - y_i^p)^2,$$

where k is the number of model parameters, p & q are the parameter values, n is the total number of observed data at each station, y_i^o & y_i^p are the observed and predicted values of ground-level ozone at the i^{th} month respectively.

In addition to this, we have also used MAPE for evaluating the performance of different model classes of ARIMA and Holt–Winters models. The MAE measures the average magnitude of the errors in a set of forecasts. RMSE is a quadratic scoring rule which measures the average magnitude of the error. The difference between the

observed and corresponding forecasted values are each squared and then averaged over the sample. It measures the accuracy as a percentage and can be calculated as the average absolute percent error for each period minus the actual values divided by actual values as follows.

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i^o - y_i^p|}{n}, \quad (5.19)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i^o - y_i^p)^2}{n}}, \quad (5.20)$$

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i^o - y_i^p}{y_i^o} \right|, \quad (5.21)$$

where n is the total number of observed data at each station, y_i^o & y_i^p are the observed and predicted values of TOL at the i^{th} month, respectively.

In order to test model accuracy, different authors used MAPE as a tool Puah *et al.* (2016). We also have used MAPE based on the developed scale of judgment for forecast model accuracy by (Lewis, 1982) as shown in Table (5.2) below.

TABLE 5.2: Scale of judgement for model accuracy

MAPE	Judgement of forecast accuracy
Less than 10%	Highly accurate
11–20%	Good forecast
21–50%	Reasonable forecast
More than 50%	Inaccurate forecast

5.3.4 Correlation Analysis

The Pearson correlation analysis is made between the actual and forecast values of surface level ozone over each station. We also visualized the monthly and seasonal linear correlation of the model with the actual values. In Equation (5.22) below, the value of R is between -1 and 1 . The positive and negative values of R indicates

the positive and negative relationships (Habtegebreal *et al.*, 2021), respectively. The correlation R is defined by

$$R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i^o - \bar{y}^o)(y_i^p - \bar{y}^p)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i^o - \bar{y}^o)^2 (y_i^p - \bar{y}^p)^2}}, \quad (5.22)$$

where n is the total number of observed data at each station, y_i^o & y_i^p are the observed and predicted values of TOL on the i^{th} month and \bar{y}^o , \bar{y}^p are the long term mean of observed and predicted values respectively.

5.4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This chapter determines a model that gives a more accurate prediction of the TOL for North-Western cluster of Ethiopia by comparing the result of the error metrics of ARIMA and additive Holt-Winters models. The methodological procedure for building these models is started from the exploratory data analysis as follows:

TABLE 5.3: Exploratory data analysis of Monthly TOL

Parameters	Stations			
	RD	AA	DK	BD
Mean	9.54	10.6	14.1	9.93
SD	1.79	1.35	1.46	1.23
Median	9.96	10.59	13.97	10.04
CV	19%	13%	10%	12%
Max	17.15	16.20	19.10	12.48
Min	6.10	7.97	10.84	6.92
Kurtosis	4.11	2.29	0.37	-0.51
skewness	1.26	0.92	0.43	-0.30

From the exploratory data analysis of Table (5.3), the values of kurtosis at Danakil Depression and Bahir Dar stations are in between -2 and +2, it can be considered

as an acceptable normally distributed data (George and Mallery, 2010), on the other hand, we need to transform the data for Addis Ababa and Ras Dashen stations as the corresponding kurtosis values exceed 2. We give the plots of the monthly TOL and the annual variation of monthly mean TOL during the study period from November 2007 to December 2019 in Figure (5.1 and 5.2) to observe the behavior of the time series.

FIGURE 5.1: Monthly TOL (2007-2019)

The exploratory analysis in Figure (5.1 and 5.2) indicated the existence of slightly decreasing linear trends over the four stations. In all stations, the data values tend to decrease over time, but the magnitude of the seasonal change remains the same, then the seasonal changes are additive. The patterns of monthly TOL have similar curved trends with two local peaks of the maximum value in May & October, while the local minimum value was during July. The monthly analysis of ground-level ozone for all stations shows higher variation throughout the study period. In all cases, the peaks were visible at regular intervals, as indicated in Figure (5.1, 5.2), and the TOL value over Danakil Depression is significantly higher than the remaining three stations TOL.

FIGURE 5.2: Annual variation of monthly mean TOL (2007-2019)

FIGURE 5.3: Autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation function of all the four stations data

The initial step of SARIMA modeling begins with the check-up of the stationarity of the process. To test the stationarity of the data, we have applied the ACF & PACF charts as shown in Figure (5.3), which indicate the values are correlated and nonstationary. This autocorrelation result shows the repetition of patterns over a year. Similarly, we also used the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (ADF) as proposed by Dobre and Alexandru (2008). From the statistical test results of ADF testing H_0 : the series is not stationary & H_1 : the series is stationary. Hence, the results become $P=0.18, 0.31, 0.38,$ and 0.35 for AA, RD, DK, and BD stations respectively. For all cases, $p > \alpha = 0.05$ indicated that it failed to reject the null hypothesis, and it confirms that all series are not stationary. Hence, we have applied the first difference method to remove both the trend and seasonality of the series. After the implementation of differencing, we also applied the statistical test again, and it confirmed the stationarity of the data.

TABLE 5.4: Best ARIMA Model, Estimated parameters of ARIMA model for TOL

Terms	AA ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)[12]		RD ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)[12]		DK ARIMA(0,1,2)(0,0,2)[12]		BD ARIMA(2,0,0)(2,1,0)[12]	
	Est.	std. err						
AR_1	-0.093	0.138	-0.510	0.080			0.257	0.087
AR_2	-0.641	0.209	-0.409	0.082			0.164	0.091
AR_3			0.410	0.077				
MA_1	0.323	0.143			-0.574	0.081		
MA_2	0.883	0.225			-0.348	0.084		
MA_3	0.159	0.112						
MA_4	0.419	0.074						
SAR_1	-0.417	0.180	0.456	0.087			-0.532	0.088
SAR_2			0.175	0.096			-0.229	0.093
SMA_1	-0.044	0.199			0.199	0.087		
SMA_2	-0.682	0.122			0.315	0.085		
drift	-0.01	0.0048						
AIC	443.46		446.89		465.62		335.94	
BIC	475.17		464.67		480.44		370.36	

From the results of ARIMA models, more than 60 Seasonal ARIMA models have been generated for the time series. The goodness of fit of such models has been assessed using the AIC and BIC. After the exhausting analysis as shown in Table (5.4), the seasonal ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)[12], ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)[12], ARIMA(0,1,2)(0,0,2)[12] and ARIMA(2,0,0)(2,1,0)[12] has been identified as the best predictive model for Addis Ababa, Ras Dashen, Danakil Depression and Bahir Dar respectively.

FIGURE 5.4: For Seasonal ARIMA model actual and predicted data of training sets

TABLE 5.5: Estimated parameter values of HW model for TOL

Stations	estimated of parameters		
	α	β	γ
AA	0.187	0.036	0.559
RD	0.366	0.025	0.583
DK	0.346	0.023	0.360
BD	0.302	0.019	0.266

The Figures in (5.4,5.6) showed that the model fits for the ARIMA and Holt-Winters model respectively. The figures in both cases indicate that the models formulated using the training data set describes the data well. Visual inspection of forecasting figures does not show differences in forecasting results clearly as indicated in Figures (5.5,5.7). However, Holt Winters Model does show higher uncertainty on the forecast values.

FIGURE 5.5: For Seasonal ARIMA model actual and forecasted data of testing sets

FIGURE 5.6: For Holt-Winter's model actual and predicted data of training sets

FIGURE 5.7: For Holt-Winter's model actual and forecasted data of testing sets

TABLE 5.6: Error Matrices of SARIMA and Holt-Winters models for TOL

Stations	Models	Error Matrices		
		RMSE	MAE	MAPE
AA	ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)[12]	1.08	0.77	7.86%
	HW $\alpha = 0.187, \beta = 0.036, \gamma = 0.559$	1.37	0.99	10.6%
RD	ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)[12]	1.08	0.82	7.76%
	HW $\alpha = 0.366, \beta = 0.025, \gamma = 0.583$	1.10	0.83	7.97%
DK	ARIMA(0,1,2)(0,0,2)[12]	1.20	0.97	6.91%
	HW $\alpha = 0.346, \beta = 0.023, \gamma = 0.360$	1.17	0.93	6.59%
BD	ARIMA(2,0,0)(2,1,0)[12]	0.90	0.69	7.07%
	HW $\alpha = 0.302, \beta = 0.019, \gamma = 0.266$	0.85	0.65	6.57%

The comparison of observed and forecasted data was performed using RMSE, MAE and MAPE to measure the accuracy and efficiency between ARIMA and Holt-Winters models for ground-level ozone forecasting. Tofallis (2015) proposed that MAPE is the most accepted measure of prediction for model selection when the data is heteroscedastic. Moreover, MAPE expresses the accuracy as a percentage of the error. It can be easier to understand than the other accuracy measures statistics.

Despite the difficulty in identifying the most suitable methods for a particular application (Msiza *et al.*, 2008), we tried our best to investigate the most efficient technique to forecast the monthly ground-level ozone over our study area. This study compares the seasonal ARIMA and Holt-Winter's models to forecast monthly TOL through performance measures. In our case, as can be seen in Table (5.6) the MAPE of the additive HW model is 10.6%, 7.97%, 6.59%, and 6.57% for the station Addis Ababa, Ras Dashen, Danakil Depression, and Bahir Dar respectively. Similarly, the MAPE of the Seasonal ARIMA models are 7.86%, 7.76%, 6.91% & 7.07% for the station Addis Ababa, Ras Dashen, Danakil Depression & Bahir Dar respectively. Even if all results were in an acceptable range, our finding leads us to propose the best model for forecasting surface level ozone is ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)[12] and ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)[12] for Addis Ababa and Ras Dashen stations respectively. While, Holt- Winters Model with ($\alpha = 0.346, \beta = 0.023 \& \gamma = 0.36$) and ($\alpha = 0.302, \beta = 0.019 \& \gamma = 0.266$) performed best for Danakil depression and Bahir Dar respectively as shown in Table (5.5).

We applied Pearson correlation analysis between the actual and forecast values of ground-level ozone over each station. We also visualized the monthly and seasonal linear correlation of the actual and the model values. The result showed a strong relationship between the observed and predicted values over all regions. We also made analysis of residuals through ACF and PACF of the residuals as follow

FIGURE 5.8: ACF and PACF of residual data from the proposed models

The analysis of residuals through ACF and PACF residuals, as shown in Figure (5.8) and the result showed that the standardized residuals are normally distributed and white noises. In this regard, we conclude that the two series have similar characteristics hence, the model considered is reliable.

The univariate approach has been used to forecast the monthly Ground-level ozone over the North-Western cluster of Ethiopia. Initially, the exploratory and autocorrelation structure has been analyzed and it reveals the non-stationarity of the data. More than 60 Seasonal ARIMA models have been generated based on time series. Goodness of fit of models has been assessed and models performance has been assessed by using AIC and BIC. After painstaking analysis, the seasonal ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)[12], ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)[12], ARIMA(0,1,2)(0,0,2)[12] and

ARIMA(2,0,0)(2,1,0)[12] has been identified as the best predictive model for Addis Ababa, Ras Dashen, Danakil Depression and Bahir Dar respectively.

We applied error evaluation metrics such as MAPE to compare the accuracy between ARIMA and Holt Winters models. The accuracies of both model forecasts were tested using the last year's test data (January 1, 2020 – December 31, 2020). Our findings lead us to propose the best model for forecasting ground-level ozone is ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)₁₂ and

ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)₁₂ for Addis Ababa and Ras Dashen stations respectively. While Holt-Winters model of $\alpha = 0.346, \beta = 0.023, \gamma = 0.36$ and $\alpha = 0.302, \beta = 0.019, \gamma = 0.266$ is better for Danakil Depression and Bahir Dar stations respectively.

The maximum errors obtained by comparing actual test data with the forecasted model values were less than 7.86% , which is in the acceptable range. Both seasonal ARIMA and Holt-Winters forecasts are very similar and performed well on the test. SARIMA model seems to perform better than Holt-Winter's model over Addis Ababa and Ras Dashen. On the other hand, the Holt-Winters model showed best results for Danakil Depression and Bahir Dar. The result is in line with (Alonso Brito *et al.*, 2021) study, as Holt–Winters models are superior modeling less variable monthly flow, while SARIMA models better forecast for highly variable periods.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

6.1 CONCLUSIONS

In this thesis we have presented the spatiotemporal distribution of total column ozone concentration over Ethiopia by analyzing the OMPS satellite data from 108 data points over Ethiopia for the period of 2012-2019 using an advanced data analysis method. The variabilities of ozone concentration in various regions including its temporal aspects are demonstrated. The results have shown that the maximum total column ozone concentration occurred during summer seasons, while the minimum measurements were recorded during the winter seasons on the North-Western and Central Ethiopia. The annual mean total column ozone concentration during the study period is found to be (261.35 ± 2.8) DU. The maximum total column ozone of 301 DU was observed on 18 August 2013 while the minimum of 216 DU was measured on on January 03, 2013.

We have also showed through spatial data clustering study that the spatial distribution of the total column ozone concentration over Ethiopia can be classified into three major representative clusters: Southern Cluster ($3.5^{\circ}N$ to $8.5^{\circ}N$ & $32.5^{\circ}E$ – $47.5^{\circ}E$), North-Eastern Cluster ($9.5^{\circ}N$ to $14.5^{\circ}N$ & $41.5^{\circ}E$ to $47.5^{\circ}E$) and North-Western Cluster ($9.5^{\circ}N$ to $14.5^{\circ}N$ & $32.5^{\circ}E$ to $40.5^{\circ}E$).

These clustering approach offers a strong foundation for studying the associated health risks as well as other environmental implications to ozone level spatial variabilities. A detailed study on comprehensive health data from various regions and their correlation with ozone concentration levels may reveal new insights. In a similar fashion, detailed investigation on a linkage between agricultural productivity of certain crops or vegetables and ozone concentration levels may furnish environmental policy makers to have strong foundation to have strict policy.

The TCO time series analysis has shown a decreasing linear trend in TCO with a depletion rate of 0.77 DU/yr, 0.73 DU/yr, and 0.43 DU/yr over North-Western, North-Eastern & Southern clusters of Ethiopia respectively. We also found a single power peak with the frequency of $f = 0.002768\text{Hz}$ with annual cyclic behavior of $\frac{1}{f} \approx 365.25$ days from spectral periodogram for the three clusters. It is important to recognize that we found only decreasing rate in all the clusters. A new study is highly recommended to resolve these trends into a trend for stratospheric and tropospheric ozone levels separately. This may lead to differentiate the drivers of these trends into natural and human-made and devise the corresponding relevant mitigation strategies.

We have also applied a univariate approach to forecast the monthly ground-level ozone over the North-Western cluster of Ethiopia. The exploratory and autocorrelation structure has been analyzed and it has revealed the non-stationarity of the data. More than 60 seasonal ARIMA models have been generated based on the time series. Goodness of fit of models and models performance have been assessed by using AIC and BIC. With this approach, the seasonal ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)[12], ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)[12], ARIMA(0,1,2)(0,0,2)[12] and ARIMA(2,0,0)(2,1,0)[12] have been identified as the best predictive models for Addis Ababa, Ras Dashen, Danakil Depression and Bahir Dar, respectively. Additional research on these models, particularly, in terms of making them models that continuously learn from the data and adjust accordingly is needed. With advance in AI, these models could be advanced further.

In this thesis we have also applied error evaluation metrics such as MAPE to compare the accuracy between ARIMA and Holt Winters models. The accuracies of these models in terms of forecasting reliably have been tested using the test data (January 1, 2020 – December 31, 2020). We have found out that the most reliable predictive models to forecast TOL measured in Addis Ababa and Ras Dashion are ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)₁₂ and ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)₁₂, respectively. Holt-Winters model of $\alpha = 0.346, \beta = 0.023, \gamma = 0.36$ and $\alpha = 0.302, \beta = 0.019, \gamma = 0.266$ is better suited to make forecast for DD & BD stations, respectively.

We have shown that the maximum errors obtained by comparing actual test data with

the forecasted model values are less than 7.86% , which is in the acceptable range.

Reliable and practical ground-level ozone monitoring and forecasting system is needed for Ethiopia regions. This thesis lays the foundation towards this goal. We have demonstrated the potential of this work and future directions it may take. With advent in technology including computing power and large data set, this work is expected to encourage ozone research and development in the region.

6.2 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE WORK

In this section, recommendations for future work are proposed based on the dissertation findings. While the temporal analysis in this dissertation focused on seasonality and trends in TCO concentration to decompose the time series, future studies should investigate long-term irregular fluctuations in ozone levels. Understanding these irregular variations is crucial for a comprehensive analysis of TCO dynamics.

Research should be conducted to identify and analyze local factors that affect total column ozone concentration. These factors may include industrial activities, urbanization, and natural phenomena specific to the region. The relationship between TCO distributions and meteorological variables over the region warrants thorough investigation. Utilizing state-of-the-art methods could provide deeper insights into how weather patterns and climatic conditions influence ozone concentrations. Furthermore, it is essential to conduct detailed studies on the vertical profile of ozone concentration. Understanding how ozone is distributed across different atmospheric layers will improve our knowledge of its formation, distribution, and depletion mechanisms. Once areas with depleted ozone are identified, it becomes crucial to focus on designing garments that provide effective UV protection for various demographics, particularly outdoor workers.

To support these studies, it is recommended that the country establish at least three ground-based instruments, strategically placed in the three clustered regions. These instruments will provide essential data for validation purposes and help in obtaining

more accurate information for the region. Implementing these recommendations will advance the understanding of total column ozone dynamics and contribute to more effective monitoring and management strategies.

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